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**Trace element variations in Cretaceous - Paleogene
sediments from Haymana, Turkey; proxies for
environmental change and Deccan volcanism**

Masterarbeit

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In memory of the COVID-19 victims

"Facts are many, but the truth is one"

- Rabindranath Tagore

ABSTRACT

Massive flood basalt volcanism is considered as the cause of major mass extinctions of the Phanerozoic by many authors. One of the most argued flood basalt events is the one that occurred during the Late Cretaceous – Early Paleogene in the Deccan Trap, India. The geochronological disputes and parallel Chicxulub bolide impact raised several criticisms over the kill capacity of the Deccan Trap (DT) eruptions although the K/Pg event wiped out several marine and terrestrial genera including the dinosaurs, ammonites, several planktons and others forever. To ascertain the impact of the Deccan Trap massive volcanism on the contemporary ecosystem it is crucial to determine the timing of the Deccan Trap volcanogenic emissions relative to the mass extinction event. Mercury (Hg) and Tellurium (Te) concentrations in sediments have been used as paleo-volcanism proxies. In this study, the potential of these two tracers has been evaluated from the western Tethys Ocean sediments of the Haymana Basin, Turkey that were deposited from the late Maastrichtian to the early Danian. Other trace elements including Ni, Zn, Mo, Re, Tl, As, Cd, REEs, Sr were also analysed from the same samples to assess the environmental stress conditions in the Haymana basin during the K/Pg crisis, and the effect on Te and Hg. The trace element data show signs of lithological control on Hg and Te; the Danian marls generally have lower concentrations of Te and Hg due to their higher carbonate content. Te/Th and Hg/Th ratios suggest that the Danian sediments however contain a higher volcanic component than the Maastrichtian. The normalised trace element ratio has revealed similarities in the Hg and Te content of the sediment samples. These Hg and Te enrichment peaks imply that the second phase eruption of the Deccan Trap large igneous province (LIP) began in the latest Maastrichtian and ended at the PO zone into the Danian whereas the subsequent eruption pulses continued until at

least the Danian P1b zone. Because of the secondary diagenesis, the Hg concentration across the sediment profile is erratic and therefore, less reliable. In contrast, the magnitude of Te enrichment in both phases of the DT LIP eruptions is in harmony with the estimated eruption rate of the Deccan lava flow and other proxies of the K/Pg boundary crisis. The environmental effects of Deccan volcanism may have amplified the effect of the Chicxulub impact. The redox element data do not show homogeneity although a brief post-K/Pg recovery of the oxygen stress has been assumed. The nutrient-type elements have implied continuation of productivity possibly by the stress-tolerant primary producers. Changes in redox conditions and paleoproductivity apparently have no significant influence on Te/Th ratios. This study shows that Te is a reliable proxy of paleo-volcanism.

Keywords: K/Pg, Volcanism, Deccan Trap, Trace Element, Hg, Te

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I. INTRODUCTION

I.A. Aim of Study:

The mass extinctions are periods of the Earth history during which rapid and widespread decline in biodiversity occurred, and usually resulted from intense changes in the climatic and environmental parameters leading to massive mortality and rapid loss of the Earth's biotic resources (Algeo & Shen 2023). During the most destructive mass extinction events of the Phanerozoic (also termed as the "Big 5" extinction events i.e., Ordovician-Silurian Extinction: ~440 Ma, Devonian Extinction: ~365 Ma, Permian-Triassic Extinction: ~250 Ma, Triassic-Jurassic Extinction: ~210, Cretaceous-Tertiary Extinction: ~66 Ma) more than 50% of species disappeared from the fossil record (Bond et al. 2014).

Large igneous province (LIP) eruptions, extraterrestrial bolide impacts, and bioevolutionary events are thought to have triggered one or more of the Big Five mass extinctions (1st order) in geological history (Algeo & Shen 2023; Foster et al. 2023). The proximate causes of all these 1st order mass extinctions were either associated with carbon-release processes (e.g., volcanism, climatic warming, ocean acidification, and reduced marine productivity) leading to a negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ excursion or carbon-burial processes (e.g., climatic cooling, increased marine productivity) that are conventionally marked enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values (Algeo & Shen 2023), indicating severe disruption of the C cycle.

The Cretaceous-Paleogene (K/Pg or K-Pg) aka Cretaceous-Tertiary (K/T) aka end-Cretaceous mass extinction (ECME) mass extinction is the most debated biological catastrophe among the Big Five mass extinction events (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019). Disagreement on the ultimate cause(s) – whether a bolide impact of extraterrestrial origin i.e., Chicxulub impact or large

igneous province (LIP) eruptions i.e., Deccan Trap (DT), have made the K/Pg mass extinction event as the most controversial among the “Big 5” (Algeo & Shen 2023; Keller 2014; Sukumaran 1998). As both the extraterrestrial impact and the LIP eruption are carbon-release events (Algeo & Shen 2023) therefore investigations are now taking place to use novel geochemical proxies other than the traditional carbon isotope ratio ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) to trace the reasons for the K/Pg mass extinction. In this context, this study tries to understand the influence of Deccan volcanism, one of the massive LIPs of the geological past, on the K/Pg extinction events, by linking the timing of Deccan volcanism to the sedimentary record of environmental change and extinction using geochemical proxies.

Figure 1: Extinction rate of marine genera over time (continuous indigo field) in comparison with the age of the LIP eruptions (orange column). (Modified from (Bond et al. 2014; Coffin et al. 2006; White & Saunders 2005)).

I.B. K/Pg Extinction Controversy:

The K-Pg mass extinction ~66 Ma has been a point of global paleontological concern as the event ended ~150 Myrs Age of the dinosaurs and paved the way for the rise, evolution and dominance of mammalian fauna (Sprain et al. 2019). Paleobiological studies revealed the annihilation of major biological clades including non-avian dinosaurs, marine and flying reptiles, and more than 20 genera of marine bivalves, bryozoans, ammonoids, gastropods, sponges, echinoids, ostracods (Schulte et al. 2010). At the base of the marine food web, the catastrophe was severe and as much as 99% of the planktonic foraminifera and 93% of nannoplankton species became extinct (Hull et al. 2020; Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019; Keller et al. 2018). However, as mentioned previously, the cause of this mass extinction is highly debated, for the occurrence of a very large bolide impact and flood basalt volcanism near its boundary (Hull et al. 2020). The extraterrestrial cause of the K/Pg mass extinction was first put forth by Alvarez et al. in 1980 (Algeo & Shen 2023; Alvarez et al. 1980; Smit & Hertogen 1980) on the basis of geochemical and petrographic evidence for impact e.g. iridium anomalies, Ni-rich-spinel peak, microspherule layers, quartz shock lamellae and fused breccia in sediments at the K/Pg boundary. A decade later discovery of the bolide impact site at Chicxulub, Mexico (Abrajevitch et al. 2015; Algeo & Shen 2023; Hildebrand et al. 1991; Molina & Llorens-Montes 2006) further fortified the notion of extraterrestrial trigger for the K/Pg catastrophe. According to the impact-extinction hypothesis, the K/Pg mass extinction was a sudden and single event while the stepwise loss of the paleontological data suggests for a combination of massive volcanism, rapid climate and sea level changes and one or more possible impacts in connection with this mass extinction (Keller et al. 2001; Keller et al. 2003). Moreover, spatiotemporal limitations of the bolide-impact studies have also made the Chicxulub impact more ambiguous (Keller et al. 2003).

The Deccan Trap as a driver of the K/Pg mass extinction was first put forth by DM McLean in 1978 (Keller et al. 2009b; McLean 1978) and this hypothesis has gained wider acceptance quite recently (Algeo & Shen 2023) due to the high-precision radiometric dating of Deccan lavas, showing that these were erupted rapidly and spanned the K/Pg. As the massive flood-basalt volcanisms triggered Permian-Triassic (P/T) and Triassic-Jurassic (T/J) mass extinction events and thus a comparable destructive effect of massive volcanism (i.e. Deccan Trap volcanism) driven K/Pg mass extinction cannot be denied (Hull et al. 2020; Keller et al. 2016).

However, opponents of the Deccan LIP eruption theory argued that it began ~250 kyr before the K/Pg extinction (Algeo & Shen 2023; Schoene et al. 2020; Sprain et al. 2019) and many of them considered that the main phase of the Deccan flood basalts (>85%) took place in between C29r/C30n boundary (~66.39 Ma) before the K/Pg impact (Chenet et al. 2007; Hull et al. 2020; Schoene et al. 2015). Based on high-precision $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating (Renne et al. 2015), it has been suggested that the Chicxulub impact triggered the most intense phase of Deccan volcanism, in which case volcanism may have amplified the environmental effects of the impact.

I.C. Stratigraphical Parameters of K/Pg Boundary:

According to the guidelines by the International Commission on Stratigraphy (ICS) and the International Union of Geological Sciences (IUGS) –the GSSP of the K/Pg boundary is the reddish layer at the base of the boundary clay section in El Kef, Tunisia (more than 7000 km from the Chicxulub crater) (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019; Sukumaran 1998). This 1-3 mm thick rusty-red oxidised layer comprising less than 1% CaCO_3 , a maximum in Total Organic Carbon (TOC), distinct alterations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and evidence of the meteorite impact (e.g., Iridium (Ir) anomaly, a peak in Ni-rich spinels, shocked quartz, impact glass spherules) (Abrajevitch et

al. 2015; Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019; Molina & Llorens-Montes 2006). In the context of the biostratigraphy, the mass extinction of the tropical and subtropical Cretaceous planktonic foraminifera and the evolution of the first Danian foraminifera species were correlated with the K/Pg boundary (Gertsch et al. 2011; Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019).

I.D. LIP and Its Lethal Effects:

Volcanically induced warming-anoxia was connected with several extinction events (e.g., the P/T, the Toarcian, the late Paleocene) of the geological past (Bond et al. 2014). Rapid volcanic eruptions of $> 100,000 \text{ km}^3$ of magma are characterised as large igneous province (LIP) events (Ernst & Youbi 2017; Grasby et al. 2015). The term LIP was first coined by Coffin and Eldholm (1991) and was revised later by Bryan and Ernst (2008) (Bond et al. 2014; Bryan & Ernst 2008; Coffin & Eldholm 1994). According to the revised version, the LIPs are primarily mafic magmatic provinces with $> 0.1 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ areal extent, igneous volumes $> 0.1 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^3$, and a maximum lifespan of $< 50 \text{ Myrs}$ (Bryan & Ernst 2008). The LIPs ($> 75\%$ of the total igneous volume) are emplaced in an intraplate setting and characterised by igneous pulses of shorter duration ($\sim 1\text{-}5 \text{ Myrs}$); the continental flood basalt provinces and oceanic plateaus are the subdivisions of the LIP (Bond et al. 2014). The LIPs represent the most voluminous manifestation of volcanism on Earth and were related to at least four of the “Big 5” extinction events of the Phanerozoic (Figure 1) (Bond et al. 2014; Wignall 2001).

The environmental, climatic and biological lethality of the LIP eruptions is mainly governed by the rapid injection of vast amounts of volcanic gas and ash into the atmosphere takes place (Bond et al. 2014); it is the magnitude of the greenhouse gas emissions like water vapour (H_2O), CO_2 , and SO_2 from volcanic eruptions, the amount of SO_2 , CO_2 , CH_4 released by

metamorphism of crust rocks by magma, and the rate of eruption that decides if a LIP is a potential giant killer (Bond et al. 2014; Keller et al. 2009b). A single LIP eruption with a volume of 1000 km^3 would inject $\sim 13 \text{ Gt}$ of CO_2 into the atmosphere which can cause significant global warming whereas; a massive LIP eruption ($10^2 - 10^3 \text{ km}^3$) could inject $\sim 1 \text{ Gt}$ of SO_2 per year into the atmosphere which after a local short-term warming up to weeks can induce cooling by producing sunlight-blocking aerosols (Bond et al. 2014; Self et al. 2005; Sigurdsson 1990). In addition, the emplacement of large volumes of magma into the crust may also release CO_2 and CH_4 as a result of metamorphism of crustal rocks (Bond et al. 2014; Svensen et al. 2009). Hydrogen chloride (HCl), hydrogen fluoride (HF), and volcanic ash containing silicate particulate matter and toxic volatile metals (As, Hg, Sb, Te, Tl, Cd) are other important deleterious products of volcanic eruptions.

I.E. Deccan Trap LIP:

The Deccan Traps is a large ($>10^6 \text{ km}^3$) continental flood basalt province in southern India and coeval with the K/Pg mass extinctions (Renne et al. 2015). The Deccan volcanism is thought to have occurred as a result of rifting of the India from the Seychelles above the Reunion mantle plume. Around 65 Ma major landmass in southern India was covered by the flows of the Deccan LIP eruptions; mountains (better known as traps) from the stepwise sequence of successive basalt lava flow in the Deccan region which is up to around 3500 m in height display that voluminous flow (Figure 2) (Keller et al. 2009a). Before erosion, the Deccan volcanic LIP had an estimated original area of 1.5 million km^2 and volume of 1.2 million km^3 (Keller 2014). Some of the lava eruptions reached over 1500 km across India and out to the Bay of Bengal via intracanyon transport (Baksi et al. 1994), forming the longest lava flows known on earth (Jay &

Widdowson 2008; Keller 2014; Self et al. 2008). Paleomagnetic studies with $^{40}\text{K}/^{40}\text{Ar}$ and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating of Deccan lava flows have revealed three main volcanic phases of DT starting in between early late Maastrichtian, to the early Danian (Chenet et al. 2007; Chenet et al. 2009; Keller 2014), and indicate that much of the lava had erupted within 1 Myr.

Figure 2: (A) Present location of Deccan Trap showing the direction of the earth's longest lava flow through the Krishna-Godavari basin to the Bay of Bengal. (Modified from (Keller 2014)). (B) High mountains formed by the Deccan Trap lava flow at Mahabaleshwar, India. (From (Keller 2014)).

The initial Deccan eruption phase (phase 1) occurred late Maastrichtian (~ 67.5 Ma, base C30N) with a ~ 1.5 Ma pause (C30N into lower C29R). This phase accounted for $\sim 6\%$ of the 3500 m-thick total Deccan lava pile (Keller et al. 2009a). The main phase of the Deccan eruption (phase 2) occurred near the end of the Maastrichtian (~ 66.03 Ma, Chron 29r) and accounted for $\sim 80\%$ of the total Deccan lava pile. This phase witnessed the world's largest lava flow after crossing ~ 1500 km across the Krishna-Godavari basin before reaching the Bay of Bengal. Afterwards, during the next 200–300 k.y. of the early Paleocene (Danian, C29R above the K-T boundary), volcanic activity was inconsequential or absent (Keller 2014). The final Deccan

eruption phase (phase 3) occurred at early Danian, (~65.12 Ma, at the base of Chron 29n), accounting for ~14% of the total Deccan lava pile ([Figure 3](#)). This phase also witnessed several of the longest lava flows spanning 1500 km across India before pouring into the Bay of Bengal ([Keller 2014](#); [Keller et al. 2012](#); [Self et al. 2008](#)).

Figure 3: Three phases of the Deccan Trap volcanic eruptions and relative thickness of lava flows. (Modified from ([Keller et al. 2012](#))).

In contrast, U-Pb zircon dating suggested four major eruptive pulses in the Deccan Trap LIP eruptions ([Schoene et al. 2020](#); [Schoene et al. 2019](#)). According to this view, the first phase of the eruption took place between ~66.3 to 66.15 Ma (Late Maastrichtian; [Figure 4](#)), the second and the main phase of the eruption (Poladpur Formation) occurred between ~66.1 to 66.0 Ma immediately before the K/Pg, and the third phase of the eruption (Ambenali Formation) occurred between ~65.9 to 65.8 Ma while the final phase of the eruption (Mahabaleswar Formation) took place in the Early Danian between ~65.6 to 65.5 Ma ([Schoene et al. 2019](#)). Both $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and U-Pb geochronology data inferred that the key phase of DT eruptions lasted ~700-800 ka duration with the activation near the C30n-C29r magnetic reversal and

declined soon after the C29r-C29n reversal (Renne et al. 2015; Schoene et al. 2020; Sprain et al. 2019).

Figure 4: Deccan Trap volcanic eruption phase and rate model prediction by U-Pb geochronology. (Modified from (Schoene et al. 2019)).

I.F. Deccan Trap Flood Basalt and K/Pg Mass Extinction:

Deccan Trap volcanism was the major cause of the K/Pg mass extinction was proposed in the year 1978 (Keller et al. 2009b; McLean 1978), before the discovery of the Chicxulub impact. In the region of the Deccan Trap, the K/Pg boundary has been identified by the shifts in planktonic foraminifera depositions along the paleo-shoreline of the Southeast Tethys Ocean in present-day quarries interbedded with Ambenali and Mahalabeshwar lava bed Formations in Rajahmundry of the Krishna-Godavari Basin and thereafter in Jhilmili (Chhindwara District, central India) (Figure 2) (Keller 2007; Keller 2014; Keller et al. 2009a). What's more, the Um

Sohryngkew section near Cherrapunji, Meghalaya NE India, ~800 km from the Deccan volcanic province, portrays one of the most complete K/Pg boundary records ([Figure 2](#)) ([Keller 2014](#); [Sukumaran 1998](#)). The Um Sohryngke section contains the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ shift, the boundary clay, a thin red layer of Ir anomaly (12 ppb), and the evolution of the first Danian foraminifera species which correlates with the global mass extinction ([Keller 2014](#)). Herein the dominance of the opportunist foraminifera *Guembelitra cretacea* and the expiration of all other planktic foraminifera from the latest Maastrichtian pointed out super-stress conditions inclusive of extreme humidity and periodic acid rains possibly as a consequence of the Deccan LIP pulses ([Keller 2014](#)).

As for other LIPs, the lethal consequences of the massive LIP eruptions at the Deccan Trap were linked with rapid environmental change resulting from the degassing of the volatiles CO_2 , and SO_2 , besides the halogens ([Keller et al. 2009b](#)). From preserved rare gas bubbles in Deccan volcanic rocks, it is projected that annual gas emission rates of Deccan lavas were more than an order of magnitude greater than the current global background volcanic emission rate ([Keller et al. 2009b](#); [Self et al. 2008](#)). Global oxygen isotope records show that during the Cretaceous part of C29r section had a warming phase with a temperature of $\sim 2.5^\circ - 5^\circ\text{C}$ (the Late Maastrichtian Warming Event) and it was followed by a cooling phase ($\sim 5^\circ\text{C}$ drop) up to the KPB while immediately after the KPB with a $\sim 100,000$ -year record of warming up to $\sim 5^\circ\text{C}$, a cooling pulse of $\sim 2^\circ - 4^\circ\text{C}$ reappeared ([Sprain et al. 2019](#)). These significant environmental changes occurred during eruption of the Deccan lavas ([Hull et al. 2020](#)).

The mass extinction crisis reached to a critical level during the main phase of the Deccan Trap eruption events. The rapid warming of 4°C in the oceans and 8°C on land ([Keller & Pardo, 2004](#)) induced dominance of disaster opportunist *Guembelitra cretacea* in shallow-marine

environments globally while the acid rains resulted in biocarbonate dissolution and extinctions of the marine biocalcifiers (Keller 2014). Closer to the hotspot of the volcanism, semiarid conditions developed in the Deccan region while the surrounding regions witnessed high precipitation, acid rains, enhanced chemical weathering and continental runoff along major influx of silt and nutrients into the oceans (Gertsch et al. 2011; Keller 2014). That could have resulted in turbid, mesotrophic to eutrophic, toxic sea waters in which except for the opportunist *Guembelitra cretacea*, other planktonic foraminifera did not survive (Keller 2014; Keller & Pardo 2004; Keller et al. 2003).

Figure 5: Possible environmental consequences of the Deccan Trap volcanic eruptions. (Modified from (Gertsch et al. 2011)).

The post-K/Pg eruptions at the Deccan Trap were associated with longer hiatuses between eruptions (Renne et al. 2015). Those longer intervals allowed the formation of sulfate aerosols and lessened volcanogenic pCO₂ through increased silicate weathering and organic carbon

burial that eventually led to rapid cooling of the environment ($> 4.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) following the mass extinction (**Figure 5**) (Hull et al. 2020; Schmidt et al. 2016; Sprain et al. 2019).

I.G. Chicxulub Impact and Deccan Volcanism:

On the basis of high-precision ^{40}Ar - ^{39}Ar dating of Deccan lavas, which showed that the main phase of Deccan volcanism (Poladpur, Ambenali and Mahabaleshwar Formations) initiated close to the K/Pg boundary and Chicxulub impact, (Renne et al. 2015; Richards et al. 2015) proposed that strong seismic waves from the Chicxulub bolide impact prompted increased volcanism specifically during the 2nd phase of the Deccan Trap eruptions at the K/Pg boundary (Chenet et al. 2009; Renne et al. 2015) which likely triggered the K/Pg mass extinction (Keller et al. 2012). It has been proposed that melting associated with meteorite impacts could drive surface volcanism (Jones 2014; Rampino 1987). Impacts >1000 km (in “basin-scale”) events can cause antipodal cratering and partial removal of crust but this antipodal focussing operated on the early earth before the Phanerozoic (Gliksn 2005; Jones 2014; Marinova et al. 2011). However, Deccan Trap volcanism was not antipodal to the Chicxulub impact site at 66 Ma (Jones 2014; Meschede et al. 2011). Although the combined Ir-Pt-Pd analyses of the K/Pg boundary clay show that the Ir is extraterrestrial in origin (Evans et al. 1993), some authors, on the basis of the Ir enrichment and presence of shocked minerals in the volcanic emissions (Sukumaran 1998), and selective extinctions of large and specialised biological groups during the K/Pg extinction do not favour the Chicxulub impact reason for the K/Pg mass extinction. If an intense phase of the Deccan volcanism was triggered by the Chicxulub impact, this would have amplified the environmental effects of the impact.

I.H. Geochemical Proxies of LIP:

At present, the geochronological data for Deccan lavas are not precise enough to rule out the hypotheses that K/Pg mass extinction was triggered by Deccan volcanism, or that the Chicxulub impact caused an increase in the intensity of the Deccan volcanism. These events, as well as the mass extinction itself, occurred within a few 10 kyr, which is beyond the resolution of radiometric dating. In the absence of zircon-bearing ash beds, it is impossible to trace the Deccan Trap LIP from the concurrent K/Pg sedimentary repositories ([Grasby et al. 2019](#)). As a result, studies are now taking place to use geochemical proxies for Deccan volcanism within K/Pg sediments, in order to link the timing of Deccan volcanism with the record of environmental change and mass extinction preserved within the same sedimentary sections. In this context, this present work tries to understand the influence of Deccan volcanism, on the K/Pg mass extinction using trace element analyses of Maastrichtian – Danian sediments.

I.H.1. Application of Trace Elements:

Globally, a peak in platinum-group elements (PGE) (e.g., Ir, Rh, Ru, Pd, Pt), siderophile elements (e.g. Co, Ni) along with other trace elements (TE) (e.g., As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Sb, Sc, V, Zn) elements are linked with an extraterrestrial impact ([Bhandari et al. 1993](#); [Martinez-Ruiz et al. 2006](#)). However elemental enrichments in the K/Pg red clay layer clearly show that an extraterrestrial impact alone cannot be the sole source of this geochemical signature ([Gertsch et al. 2011](#)). Previous geochemical signature of the K/Pg boundary layer across the Cretaceous-Tertiary transition Um Sohryngkew section in Meghalaya, India discovered condensed sedimentation (Phosphorus (P) enrichment), redox fluctuation (As, Co, Fe, Pb, Zn, and to a lesser extent Ni and Cu) and volcanism (Na/K, K/(Fe+Mg), Ca/Na and Mg/Na) along with an

extraterrestrial signal (Ni and all Platinum Group Elements (PGEs) that seemed to occur afterwards of the Chicxulub impact (Gertsch et al. 2011). Moreover, closer to the hotspot, except for the Um Sohryngkew section, the other K/Pg boundaries in India reveal insignificant Ir records and do not specify any bolide impact (Bhandari et al. 1993) at the K/Pg boundary. As well as the Ir has been found in volcanic emissions (Sukumaran 1998). In this regard, growing interest in using the novel geochemical proxies to fingerprint the major volcanisms in the sedimentary records as “LIP marks” (Grasby et al. 2019). With the discovery of Hg as a proxy of past volcanic eruptions (Grasby et al. 2019; Selin 2009; Sial et al. 2020) these efforts have received a further impetus to address the K/Pg mass extinction debate.

It was coincidental that Hildebrand and Boynton were the earliest investigators who studied Hg across K/Pg extinction events although in support of their proposition about bolide impact-led intensified acid rain and leaching of metals at the K/Pg boundary (Hildebrand & Boynton 1989). The Deccan Trap flood basalt emission had induced the Hg spikes at the K/Pg boundary was anticipated around a decade ago (Grasby et al. 2019; Nascimento-Silva et al. 2011). Thereafter, the elemental mercury concentration (Hg^0) has been widely used to trace volcanic inputs to paleodepositional systems in shallow to deep marine as well as terrestrial areas (Percival et al. 2015; Percival et al. 2017; Shen et al. 2020). Long residence time (0.5 to 2 yrs) in the atmosphere for allowing wide dispersal after a major volcanic eruption, rapid removal ($10\text{-}10^2$ yrs) from ocean surface water to sediment through adsorption onto organic matter and/or other minerals, and mass-independent isotope variations (^{198}Hg , ^{199}Hg) with distinctive values for the volcanogenic sources make the volcanogenic Hg in sediments a reliable proxy for the intensity of volcanism (Zhao et al. 2022).

The estimations revealed that the Hg emission rate from the past LIP was significantly higher

than the average contributions (75 to 700 Mg/ya Hg into the atmosphere) of modern volcanic eruptions ([Grasby et al. 2019](#)). For example, the Hg release from the Siberian Traps LIP event (~252 Mya) was ~3800 MT (~14× increase over modern background) ([Grasby et al. 2015](#)) and from the Karoo–Ferrar LIP eruption (~300–500 kyr) was ~150 MT ([Percival et al. 2015](#)). Hence, the Hg enrichment in marine sediment is a potential tracer of voluminous volcanism during the mass extinctions e.g., Siberian Traps LIP (~250 Ma) at the P/T, Central Atlantic Magmatic Province (~201 Ma), the Emeishan LIP (~260 Ma) at the Guadalupian–Lopingian Boundary and the others ([Regelous et al. 2020](#); [Sanei et al. 2012](#); [Shen et al. 2020](#)). Usually in shallow water sediment homogenization by bioturbation yields Hg enrichment and faunal turnover is synchronous whereas in deep water there was a large time lag between the initial Hg pulse extinction horizon ([Shen et al. 2020](#)). Overall, the Hg concentration in sedimentary rocks (mostly the shales) is 62.4 µg/kg which is higher than the average value (50 µg/kg) of the upper continental crust.

The principle of using the Hg fingerprint for volcanism is based on the fact that it is widespread and deposited in marine sediments. But its redox-sensitivity, affinity to organic matter (OM), and sensitivity to post-depositional (secondary) diagenesis complicate the use of Hg as a definite signature of the voluminous volcanic eruptions ([Grasby et al. 2019](#)). Mercury may also be highly enriched in accessory minerals in sediments such as pyrite. There are significant differences in the measured Hg profiles across the K/Pg boundary at different sediment sections worldwide ([Font et al. 2022](#); [Keller et al. 2020](#); [Li et al. 2023](#); [Sial et al. 2013](#)). This implies that Hg may not be a reliable proxy for Deccan volcanism at the K/Pg boundary.

Besides the Hg, there are some other volatile trace elements including As, Bi, Cd, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se, Te, Tl, and Zn which, like Hg, are highly enriched in volcanic gas ([Rampino et al. 2017](#);

[Regelous et al. 2020](#); [Symonds et al. 1987](#); [Zelenski et al. 2014](#)) and their assessment from the sedimentary records can help to overcome the limitations of the Hg fingerprinting of the LIP eruptions ([Grasby et al. 2019](#)). However, as many of these elements are also sensitive to sediment mineralogy, redox state and productivity it is necessary to evaluate the effects of these factors using complete trace element analyses of sediments.

For instance, although Ni in Permian – Triassic sediments has been used as a proxy for Siberian Trap volcanism ([Rampino et al. 2017](#)), increased periods of enhanced productivity-induced higher organic matter can accelerate the scavenging of Ni, Zn, Cd and Cu through the water column, propel their complex formations and boost their high flux in marine sediment ([Tribovillard et al. 2006](#)). Absorption on Mn-oxyhydroxides in the water column can also enrich Ni, Zn, Pb and Co in marine sediments ([Calvert & Pedersen 1996](#)). The redox state of the sediment bed and overlying water crucially control the redox-sensitive elements like Tl, Mo, U, and V ([Calvert & Pedersen 1996](#)). More recently, Te in Permian – Triassic sediments has been used as a proxy for Siberian LIP volcanism ([Regelous et al. 2020](#)). However, Te is also highly enriched in the Fe-Mn oxy-hydroxide component of sediments ([Hein et al. 2003](#)). Many trace elements are highly sensitive to sediment lithology and mineralogy (e.g., Zr and Hf in zircon, REE and Th in monazite, Nb, Ta in rutile, and chalcophile trace elements in sulfide) ([Regelous et al. 2020](#)). Therefore, measurement of a large number of different trace elements in sediments is needed, in order to evaluate the effects of sediment mineralogy and environmental conditions, before using a particular trace element as a proxy for volcanism ([Regelous et al. 2020](#)).

The application of novel geochemical proxies has now gained prominence to trace the LIP events across the Phanerozoic. However, in the context of the K/Pg mass extinctions, the

published Hg data are an ambiguous proxy for Deccan volcanism, as different Hg profiles across the K/Pg boundary at different localities worldwide differ significantly (e.g. ([Font et al. 2022](#); [Keller et al. 2020](#); [Percival et al. 2018](#); [Sial et al. 2013](#))). Hence in this work, a high-resolution record of the concentrations of 40 trace elements including Hg, Te and Ni in the sediment samples of the Haymana basin, (within the northern Neo Tethys realm), Turkey covering the late Maastrichtian to the early Danian interval (K-Pg transition) have been analysed and reported.

II. LOCATION

II.A. Geographical Setting:

The sampling site in the Haymana basin is about 60 km southwest of Ankara city and 5 km northeast of Haymana town (Figure 6). During the k/Pg transition, this location was in the vicinity of the tropical zone (Figure 7). The planktonic to benthic ratio (P:B) of the foraminifera test >150 μ m size fraction has yielded ~ 400 m paleodepth (upper bathyal zone) for the studied section of Haymana basin (Karabeyođlu et al. 2019).

II.B. Geological Setting:

The Haymana basin developed as a fore-arc basin as a result of the northward dipping subduction of the Neo-Tethys Ocean beneath the Pontides at the convergent plate boundary between the African plate and Eurasian Plate (Figure 8). The basin consists of more than 5 km thick upper Campanian-middle Eocene siliciclastic deposit while its basement rocks are composed of deformed pre-Jurassic Karakaya Complex that is covered by carbonates from the Lower Jurassic to Cretaceous and succeeded by Upper Cretaceous flysch deposits (Figure 9) (Karabeyođlu et al. 2019). The bottom-to-top lithostratigraphic units of the K/Pg transition phase of the Haymana area are the Upper Cretaceous Haymana and Beyobası formations and the Paleocene Kartal, Çaldađ and Yeşilyurt formations (Demircan & Görmüş 2020). In the Haymana basin, the upper Maastrichtian is represented by monotonous mudstones whereas the lower Danian is dominated by marls; the K-Pg boundary lies in between these two units and is marked by a 2-3 mm thick reddish clay layer (Figure 10) (Karabeyođlu et al. 2019).

Figure 6: (A-B) Location map of the Haymana basin in Turkey.

Figure 7: Paleogeographical map of the Haymana basin at the K/Pg event (~66.03 Ma).

Figure 8: Maastrichtian palaeogeography and locations of the Haymana basin (pink asterisk) and surrounding regions (yellow squares) in Turkey. (Modified from (Özcan et al. 2021)).

Figure 9: Geological map of the Haymana and surrounding region. (Modified from (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019)).

Figure 10: Succession from Maastrichtian mudstones to Danian marls after the 2-3 mm thick reddish oxidized layer of K/Pg boundary. (From (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019)).

III.C. Biozone Setting:

The foraminifera biozone for the sampled profile of the Haymana basin has been determined from the personal communication of Prof. T. Adatte (Adatte 2023) who provided the samples for this study. This shows around 8 m *Plummerita hantkeninoides* (benthic foraminifera) dominant zone at Maastrichtian along some fraction of *Guembelitra cretacea*, *Heterohelix* and *Globigerinelloides*. The rapid and intense environmental stress at the K/Pg boundary red layer in the Haymana basin (supposedly as a consequence of the Chicxulub impact or Deccan Trap LIP eruption) was linked with the bloom of the opportunistic ecological generalists (R-strategist) foraminifera *Guembelitra cretacea* and the decline of ecological specialists particularly the larger, ornamented, biserial heterohelicids (K-strategists) (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019). This observation is in agreement with an earlier report (Keller & Pardo 2004) about very high *G. cretacea* blooms (40-80%) in the tropics and subtropics at the Danian P0 Zone. The

post K/Pg red layer was succeeded by *Parvularugoglobigerina eugubina* (planktonic foraminifera) biozone at the lowermost Danian (P α) (Figure 11).

Figure 11: The relative geochronology, biozone and stratigraphy of the Haymana basin sampling zone; the oldest sample was younger than 66.67 Ma and the youngest sample was older than 62.7 Ma. Haymana basin lithostratigraphy and corresponding foraminifera biozone have been achieved from personal communication of Prof. T. Adatte, 2023.

It has to be noted that the absolute ages of the biozones for the K/Pg section in different literature are not in harmony. According to some authors, P1b zone is much older than 62.7 Ma and P1a, P0 zones of the Danian had a duration of 380 kyr while the CF1 zone of

Maastrichtian (*P. hantkeninoides*) lasted for 160 kyr ([Keller 2014](#); [Mateo et al. 2016](#)). While some others mentioned that CF1 lasted 160-300 Kyr, P0+P1a is 120-150 kyr, P1b670 kyr-590kyr (e.g. [Punekar et al. 2014](#)). Thus, the amount of time represented by the Danian sediments in this section could be as short as 820 kyr, and the Maastrichtian less than 160 kyr. However, those records (e.g. [Keller 2014](#)) assumed 65.5 Ma as the K/Pg boundary layer age but herein it is assumed as 66.03 Ma following more recent studies (e.g. [Schoene et al. 2019](#)).

III. METHODOLOGY

III.A. Sample Preparation:

The following steps were practised to prepare the sample for analysis in the ICP-MS. Beforehand of transferring the powdered sample into Teflon beakers, the sample containers and the beakers were put under an electrostatic device to prevent the loss of powder from the beaker (Figure 12). Around 0.05 g of powdered sample was weighed accurately (to within 0.0001 g) into a marked Teflon beaker, and digested in 1 mL 15M HNO₃ and 3 mL 12M HF in a sealed beaker on a hotplate overnight at 100-120°C (Figure 12). When the solution evaporated to initial dryness at 120°C, then 2 mL of 15M HNO₃ was then added to the sample, and evaporated to near dryness. This step was repeated twice. The sample solutions were then quantitatively transferred to 250 mL high-density polyethylene bottles and diluted to 200 g with Milli-Q (MQ) water. The final solution strength was 2% HNO₃ + 0.001 M HF with total dissolved solids of about 250 µg/mL. All reagents were distilled in Teflon stills and diluted with MQ 18.2 Ohm water. The precise dilution factor (about 4000) was calculated for each sample from the weights of the sample powder and the final solution.

III.B. Analytical Methods:

The trace element concentrations of those final solutions were run and determined by Thermo Scientific X-series 2 quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (QICP-MS) at the GeoZentrum Nordbayern, Erlangen (Figure 12). The quadrupole filters out the sample ions based on the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of the target sample and transfers them to an ion detector. The sample aerosol was dried using a Teflon nebuliser (Cetac Aridus

2 desolvating nebulizer system) (Figure 12); this system increases sensitivity and reduces molecular interferences. Furthermore, to reduce the washout times of the samples an ESI SC-2 DX FAST was used. Finally, the samples were run and analysed by Dr. Marcel Regelous at GeoZentrum Nordbayern, Erlangen. Instrument drift was corrected by using a mixed Be-In-Rh-Bi internal standard. Precision was 1 – 5% for most elements. Accuracy was monitored by measuring the standard rock sample SCo-1 (shale), and was better than 5% for most elements including Te. Mercury concentrations on the same samples were determined by T. Adatte using atomic fluorescence spectrometry at the University of Lausanne.

Figure 12: (A-H) Analytical methodology [A-Electrostatic device; B-Measuring 0.05 g powdered sample in Sartorius analytic weighing instrument; C - Adding 1 mL 15M HNO₃; D-Adding 3 mL 12M HF; E-Drying in hotplate; F- QICP-MS at the GeoZentrum Nordbayern; G- Sample washing and transferring using ESI SC-2 DX FAST; H-Sample passing through Cetac Aridus 2 desolvating nebulizer system.

IV. RESULT

The variations in the trace elements' concentrations of the Haymana basin sediments with height (age) across the K/Pg transition are shown in (Figure 13, Figure 14).

The Hg concentration ranges from about 10 ppb to 48 ppb; the maximum concentration (48.2 ppb) of Hg is observed in the late Maastrichtian -230 cm below the K/Pg boundary clay; intermittent peaks are present throughout the observed late Maastrichtian with the oldest peak is located between -740 cm and -730 cm. Additionally, -240 cm (43.4) and -1 cm (42.0) - below the K/Pg, has also high Hg concentrations. The Danian marls generally have lower Hg concentrations than the Maastrichtian mudstones, with two moderately enriched peaks between +40 cm and +80 cm (P α zone) and +230 cm (P1b zone), and the lowest concentration is at the top of the sampled section at +460 cm (P1b zone).

Elements such as Th and Nb which are mainly contained in the detrital component of sediments and unaffected by redox conditions or productivity, have very similar variations with depth. Their concentrations are generally high and uniform within the late Maastrichtian mudstones and lower and more variable in the Danian marls. Zr, Ta, and Li show very similar behaviour to Th and Nb.

The Te concentration is highest (170.50 ppb) in the K/Pg boundary clay. Unlike Th and Nb, the Te concentrations increase in the latest Maastrichtian (200 cm below the K/Pg) until the K/Pg boundary. The lowest Te concentrations are observed in the Early Danian (P α zone), 100-200 cm above the K/Pg. Overall, the absolute concentration of the Te range in the Haymana basin varies by a factor of around 3.

Figure 13: Concentrations of trace elements Thorium (Th), Mercury (Hg), Tellurium (Te), Rhenium (Re), Niobium (Nb) from vertical sediment profile of the Haymana basin during the K/Pg transition; unless mentioned as ppb the concentration unit is ppm. The red dashed line represents the K/Pg boundary layer.

Figure 14: (A-D) Vertical profiles of trace elements in Haymana sediment basin during the K/Pg transition. A: Concentrations of Lanthanum (La), Ytterbium (Yb), Samarium (Sm), Neodymium (Nd), Zircon (Zr); B: Concentrations of Thallium (Tl), Antimony (Sb), Tantalum (Ta), Strontium (Sr), Lithium (Li); C: Concentrations of the trace elements Molybdenum (Mo), Vanadium (V), Uranium (U), Arsenic (As), Chromium (Cr); D: Concentrations of the trace elements Zinc (Zn), Nickel (Ni), Cadmium (Cd), Copper (Cu), Barium (Ba). Unless mentioned as ppb the concentration unit is ppm. The red dashed lines represent the K/Pg boundary layer.

The variations in Re contents are unlike those of Th, Nb, Hg and Te. Re contents are generally lower in the late Maastrichtian sediments than in the younger Danian mudstones. A well-defined peak in Re (up to 30 ppb) occurs near the base of the section at between -750 cm to -730 cm. The Re varies by a factor of around 89 in this analysis. The PCA analysis of the concentration of the elements has also kept the Re away from the others ([Figure 15](#)).

Figure 15: PCA graph depicting contribution range of the elements in Haymana basin according to their concentration.

The concentrations of the Rare Earth Elements (REE) like Yb, Sm and others are all similar and resemble those of Th and Nb with generally lower and more variable concentrations in the Danian compared to the Maastrichtian, except that the highest REE concentrations occur at -20 cm below the K/Pg and all have a declining trend in the post-K/Pg profile.

Strontium, which unlike Th, Nb and the REE, is often enriched in the carbonate fraction of sediments, behaves differently to Th and Nb. The post-K/Pg Danian marls have higher Sr concentrations than the late Maastrichtian mudstones.

Elements that are sensitive to redox conditions (e.g. Mo, U, Tl) and/or to variations in paleoproductivity (e.g. Zn, Cd), also behave differently to Th and Nb (Figure 13, Figure 14). The chalcophile trace elements Tl and Sb have an overall decreasing trend towards the early Danian following the K/Pg boundary where they have the highest concentration and it is similar to that of the siderophile element Ni. In the sampled section of the Haymana basin Ni, Sb and Tl vary by a factor of about 10, 15 and 5 respectively.

The nutrient types of elements like Zn, Cd, and Cu have distinct vertical variations (Figure 13, Figure 14). However, in all of them except for the Cd, the highest concentration is observed in the K/Pg boundary clay. In the Cd profile, after the 0.6917 value in the K/Pg boundary clay, the concentrations increase along the Danian section with the highest value at +380 cm (P1b zone). Contrastingly Zn and Cu have an overall declining pattern and in the post-K/Pg profile, the Zn concentration has three higher ranges at +240 cm, +230 cm of the P1b zone and +90 cm (P α zone). In this observation, the absolute concentration of Zn, Cd, Cu and Ba vary by a factor of around 3, 8, 3 and 65 respectively.

For the redox-sensitive trace elements, the highest values are recorded at the K/Pg boundary (Figure 13, Figure 14). Among them, the Mo concentration is rather monotonous while for the As, V, U and Cr there is an overall decreasing pattern. However, for the U and As, the pre-K/Pg concentrations are lower than that of the respective Danian values. The absolute concentration of Mo, U, V, As and Cr vary by a factor of around 200, 3, 3, 19 and 4 respectively in this study. In summary, concentrations of most of the trace elements are higher in the Maastrichtian mudstones than in the overlying Danian marls, and for many elements, the highest values are observed in the 2-3 mm thick K/Pg boundary clay.

Figure 16: Correlation test of Hg, Te, Re and Nb with Th. All have positive correlation but for the Te and Re the correlations are not significant whereas the correlation of Nb and Th is highly positive.

Figure 17: Correlation test of Sm with Yb, Mo with Re and Sr and Ni with Th. Sm and Yb has a positive significant correlation whereas Mo and Re correlation excluding the value at K/Pg boundary layer is negative and not significant; the Sr and Ni have negative significant correlation with Th.

Figure 18: Pre-K/Pg and post-K/Pg variation of Hg, Te, Re, Nb, TI, Sr with Th (a-f) and variation of Th, Nb with Zr (g-h). The hollow green triangles represent the pre-K/Pg values, the hollow orange squares represent the post-K/Pg values, and the red solid circle represents the values at K/Pg boundary layer.

V. DISCUSSION

V.A. Effect of Sediment Mineralogy on Trace Element Profiles:

While the trace elements cannot affect the physical and chemical properties of any system but their geochemical properties are profoundly important in understanding the natural forces that have shaped the earth's evolution to its present form ([White 2020](#)). The trace element composition of sediments is affected by numerous factors. Sediment mineralogy has a first-order effect on the concentration of many trace elements. The fine-grained detrital (clay) component of sediments contains higher concentrations of most trace elements including Th, Nb and the REE, whereas quartz and biogenic carbonate have much lower concentrations of most elements, with the exception of Sr which substitutes for Ca in carbonate. The carbonate:detrital ratio therefore has an important control on trace element concentrations. In addition, environmental effects including redox state and productivity may influence the concentrations of some elements including Mo, U, Zn, and Cd (e.g. ([Tribovillard et al. 2006](#))). Trace element records from sediment can be used to identify the relative timing and intensity of past volcanism but to ascertain if the trace element flux had origin from volcanic emissions it is important to consider that the biological and environmental processes can also influence the concentration of those trace elements ([Regelous et al. 2020](#)).

The depth profiles of certain trace elements (e.g. Ir, Pt) have been in use to address the bolide impacts on K/Pg mass extinction for a good amount of time ([Alvarez et al. 1980](#); [Bhandari et al. 1993](#); [Martinez-Ruiz et al. 2006](#); [Smit & Hertogen 1980](#); [Sukumaran 1998](#)). As sediment contains an array of elements therefore its chert (silica) and carbonate content are the important riders of the concentrations of elements that are not contained in silica and carbonate. As the mass

extinctions eliminate the biogenic silica producers (radiolaria and diatom) and/or biogenic carbonate producers (foraminifera, coccolithophore) so, those events could augment the concentrations of several trace elements in times of the critical transitional phases of the earth's history.

In the Haymana section, the Late Maastrichtian mudstones have generally lower carbonate contents than the overlying Early Danian marls (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019). The strong positive correlation between Th and Nb ($R_{Nb/Th}=0.958$; Figure 16) and the negative correlation between Th and Sr (Figure 17) indicate that the factor of 3-4 variation in Th and Nb is largely controlled by variations in the detrital to carbonate fraction, which was higher in the Late Maastrichtian mudstones. The correlation graphs of Nb with Th of this study in general, do not indicate the presence of any Th-rich mineral like monazite in the Haymana sediment.

In contrast to Nb, other elements do not correlate so well with Th. The Re to Th concentration has both lower and higher values in post-K/Pg and the correlation is not significant ($R_{Re/Th} = -0.105$; Figure 16, Figure 18). This indicates that Re concentration was influenced by some environmental processes like redox state that had no control on Th. The Te to Th concentration has a similar pattern but a positive significant correlation ($R_{Te/Th} = 0.590$) with concise pre-K/Pg values (Figure 16, Figure 18). Moreover, the intercept in both scenarios is away from the origin. So, to comment further on the biogenic carbonate contribution, correlation information of the other trace elements like Hg, Tl, Nb and Sr to Th have been gathered; here the first three elements represent higher concentrations in the late Maastrichtian but the Sr has higher values in the post-K/Pg Danian sediments. The significant positive correlations of Hg, Tl and Nb with Th ($R_{Hg/Th} = 0.764$, $R_{Tl/Th} = 0.613$, $R_{Nb/Th}=0.958$) along the position of the respective intercept near the origin suggest for an increase of biogenic

carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) content at post-K/Pg and therefore the respective concentrations may vary due to the dilution effect of CO_3^{2-} .

The Sr to Th ratio with a significant negative correlation ($R_{\text{Sr/Th}} = -0.655$; **Figure 17**) results from an increase in the carbonate/clay ratio; the post-K/Pg rise in Sr to Th ratio reflects the higher carbonate content in the Danian marls (**Figure 18**). Further to mention that the concentration of Th and Nb are well correlated with Zr in this study with the higher values at the pre-K/Pg profile and the same trend has been observed for Zr and Hf correlation (**Figure 18**) which can also be explained by higher carbonate contents, and therefore lower Zr, Nb, Th in the post - K/Pg Danian marls. The Mo to Re ratio (after removing the highest enrichment value of Mo in the K/Pg boundary layer) with insignificant negative correlation ($R_{\text{Mo/Re}} = -0.156$; **Figure 17**) reveals that Re and Mo concentration was not controlled by a similar reason.

Previous observation from Festningen sediments during the end Permian mass extinction has reported a general positive correlation of Te and Nb with Th due to variations in the biogenic silica content. In the Haymana basin, a positive correlation between Te and Th is also observed, indicating that variations in carbonate content also influence Te concentrations, but the correlation is not as significant as between Th and Nb. Therefore, Te are likely also influenced by some natural force like volcanism. Since sparse information about the properties of volcanogenic Te is available therefore, further observation is required to infer such behaviour; however, its absolute concentration (**Figure 13**) informs a post K/Pg enrichment which can be explained by the third phase of the Deccan Trap eruption.

Considering the fact while studying the trace elemental concentration from the K/Pg boundary and the imminent upsection of the Haymana sediment profile, to remove the effects of the carbonate dilution effect, the chalcophile element concentrations were

normalised to Th as the Th is not contained in carbonate and silica (SiO₂) and not enriched in the volcanic emissions (Regelous et al. 2020; Zelenski et al. 2014). For elements that are not contained in carbonate, the element/Th ratio is unaffected by changes in the carbonate content of the rock. The Th content is more sensitive over Al to the presence of accessory mineral phases but the excellent positive correlation between Th and Nb shows that mineralogical effects on Th content are negligible. In addition, the Th normalisation method shortens the analytical time as both the Th and trace element can be measured from the same sample dissolution using the same analytical method (Regelous et al. 2020).

Regarding the Re/Th variation across the studied profile is similar to the Re concentration profile (91 ppb/ppm and 89 respectively), indicating that variations in Re, not Th control the range in Re/Th. Except for one enrichment peak at around between -750 cm to -740 cm of the Maastrichtian and another at +210 cm of the Danian (P1b zone) (Figure 19), there is no systematic variation of Re distribution across the Haymana basin profile. The inconsistent distribution of Re/Th parallel to the Siberian Trap eruption has also been reported earlier (Regelous et al. 2020). Despite the presence of Re in carbonate-free environment and volcanogenic aerosol, its complex distribution in the Haymana basin, particularly the absence of enrichment at the K/Pg boundary is difficult to explain. Oxidation state, environmental control or even instrumental sensitivity could be the reason for such behaviour. Across the post-K/Pg boundary, the Re/Th value increases by about a factor of 2.

The variations of Sr (minor conservative element) and Li (major conservative element) are used as weathering and detrital inputs alongside tracing muffin releases (Adloff et al. 2021). In the Haymana basin Sr and Li concentration, particularly from the K/Pg boundary onwards to the early Danian, show sharp disparity. For the Li, the absolute concentrations decrease by a

factor of 4 while the Sr concentration rises by about a factor of 2 in the post-K/Pg profile (Figure 14). The increase in Sr is likely due to the higher carbonate content of the Danian sediments. During the Late Maastrichtian dry seasonal conditions prevailed in the Deccan region (Keller 2014); therefore, the lesser weathering phenomena, together with an increase in the carbonate content could cause the decline in Li values in the studied upsection since the K/Pg event. The observation from the Um Sohryngkew section in NE India which was away from the Deccan volcanic hotspot showed signs of excessive acid rain during the Deccan LIP pulses (Keller 2014). The Sr /Th ratio (Figure 17) also suggests an increase in CO_3^{2-} in the Danian. As carbonate can also influence Sr and U concentrations of sediments (Regelous et al. 2020) so, it could be possible that the flux of assemblages of the planktonic bicarbonate shells resulted in enrichment of the Sr concentration in the Danian.

The concentration variability of the REEs in the Haymana basin has followed the trend of Th and Nb i.e., a more scattered range but in general lower concentrations in the Danian section (Figure 14). Some higher values of Sm over Yb resulted in some positive peaks of Sm/Yb across the depth profile with three major ones in the down section at -15 cm to -20 cm, -130 cm and -220 cm of the late Maastrichtian and relatively three minor peaks at +260 cm, +360 cm, +440 cm of the early Danian (P1b zone) although both in the Maastrichtian mudstone and the Danian marl, the Sm/Yb does not vary significantly in respect to the K/Pg value (Figure 19). As phosphate can retain high Sm/Yb (Regelous et al. 2020) so, the possibility of phosphatic phases (i.e., accumulation of phosphorus compound in marine sediment from the bodies of dead organisms like planktons) because of temperature rise, acid rain, and anoxia could not be ruled out. The intermittent Sm/Yb peaks -220 cm to -130 cm of the Maastrichtian thus could also be linked with the onset of second eruptive pulses of the Deccan Trap volcanism. In

summary, the enrichment of the REEs at the K/Pg boundary is similar to that of Th profile and the relative drop in the REEs like La, Nd, Yb, and Sm in this study compared to the previous observations of the parallel sediment profile in India and Italy ([Bhandari et al. 1993](#)) is likely due to an increase in the carbonate content of the Danian sediments in the Haymana basin ([Figure 20](#)).

In general, the chalcophile elements are depleted in the Earth's crust and concentrated in the core. Therefore, it is expected that aerosols from pulses of massive volcanisms are enriched with these elements compared to the continental crust ([White 2020](#)) and so the volcanic atmospheric inputs into marine water should result in a detectable enrichment of chalcophile critical elements. The chalcophile trace elements Se, Te, As, Sb, and Re are more enriched in volcanic gases over less volatile elements like Ni, Zn etc. ([Regelous et al. 2020](#); [Symonds et al. 1987](#)). However environmental conditions like absorption, redox state, and productivity have a major control on their concentration profile in the sediment. For instance, absorption onto Mn-oxyhydroxides in the water column may enrich Ni, Zn, Pb and Co in marine sediments ([Calvert & Pedersen 1996](#); [Regelous et al. 2020](#)). The redox state (level of O₂ concentration) of the overlying water and sediment regulates the concentration of the redox-sensitive elements like Thallium (Tl), Mo, U, and V ([Calvert & Pedersen 1996](#)). On the other hand, productivity regulates the concentration of nutrient-type elements like Ni, Zn, Cd, and intermediate element Cu. A high abundance of primary producers in marine water promotes the formation of organo-metallic compounds, scavenging from the water column and enhancing elemental flux into the sediment ([Tribovillard et al. 2006](#)). Before using chalcophile trace elements as proxies for volcanism, the effects of redox and paleoproductivity must be evaluated.

Figure 19: Depth profile of trace element concentrations normalised to Th (to eliminate SiO₂ dilution effect) of the Haymana basin during the K/Pg transition; Sm was normalised to Yb as per convention. The red dashed horizontal lines represent the K/Pg boundary layer.

Figure 20: Comparison of few trace elements at different K/Pg sampling sites.

V.B. Interpretation of Paleoredox Conditions from Trace Element Proxies:

The redox tracers help to identify the oxidising and reducing gradients (oxic-suboxic-anoxic-euxinic) of the environment. Temporal trends of those tracers for example the redox-sensitive trace elements in sedimentary archives can therefore detect the past redox conditions of the depositional basin (Tribovillard et al. 2006). In this present study, the ratio of normalised redox-sensitive elements for example, TI/Th and Mo/Th distribution patterns of the Haymana basin look analogous (Figure 19) although the highest value (0.13) of the former is at +170 cm of the early Danian (P α zone) while the latter has the highest value (4.86) at the K/Pg boundary layer. Both the ratios have less systematic variations, particularly in the Maastrichtian and the lowest value was observed immediately after the K/Pg boundary. Therefore, it could be possible that the local oxidation state of water could control the TI and Mo concentrations. It has been further observed that the TI/Th varies by about a factor of 2 and Mo/Th varies by a factor of 162 and a high difference developed due to a larger enrichment peak of the Mo/Th at the K/Pg boundary. Since Mo is enriched in chondritic meteorites relative to the Earth's

crust, an extraterrestrial impact could also induce the extreme enrichment spike of Mo in the KPg boundary clay.

Other than the volcanogenic emissions, the redox state of the water column regulates the Mo, V, and U concentrations in the marine sediment repositories (Regelous et al. 2020). The As, Cr and Co also are used as redox tracers however, they have a strong detrital influence (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Mo concentration is known to increase in times of anoxia (Bond et al. 2014; Regelous et al. 2020) and high Mo indicates the presence of sulfurised organic matter in the deposition bed. Therefore, it is widely used as a proxy redox potential (Tribovillard et al. 2006). However, in this study except for the very high value at the K/Pg boundary the systematic variation of absolute and normalised Mo concentration is monotonous across the Haymana sediment profile and thus it is not possible to infer the redox conditions using Mo (Figure 14, Figure 19). In contrast, despite this insignificant distribution range, the absolute Mo concentration varies by about a factor of 200 and the normalised Mo concentration varies by a factor of about 162 across the Haymana basin because of its extreme enrichment acme at the K/Pg boundary. The highly enriched Mo value at the K/Pg boundary is most likely induced by bolide impact, since Mo is not especially enriched in volcanic gas. Mo enrichment is indicative of a euxinic depositional environment (Robbins et al. 2016) and therefore, it could be possible that the Tethys water overlying the Haymana basin experienced severe oxygen stress at the K/Pg boundary. However, it has been found that in moderately to strong deep water, Mo concentration may not reflect the redox potential because of the basin reservoir effect (Tribovillard et al. 2006). The paleo bathymetry of the studied sediment section was within 400 m (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019) and on that account, the basin effect was not a barrier to the lack of systematic variation in the studied Mo-profile. To know the redox phase of the

depositional environment other paleoredox proxies e.g., U, V, As, Cr of the Haymana basin were therefore surveyed.

The U, which has the least detrital influence, in the Haymana basin has a post-K/Pg enrichment with the highest absolute concentration at the K/Pg boundary and afterwards, three acmes with intermittent decline were observed at +80 cm (P α zone), +260 cm and +360 cm (P1b zones) of the early Danian whereas the late Maastrichtian profile represents the most depleted U concentrations ([Figure 14](#)). Across the profile, the absolute concentration of U varies by a factor of about 3. As the authigenic U enrichment process occurs only in sediment under anoxic and reduced conditions ([Tribovillard et al. 2006](#)) therefore the enrichment peaks in the Danian section of the Haymana basin are suggestive of the concomitant anoxic environments but then the intermittent values are indicative of reoxidation and/or decrease in organic matter flux from the surface water because of the recovery of the base members of the marine food web. Mineralogical fractions of sediment as well as the detrital clay can regulate the trace elements concentration in the deposition bed. For instance, the Fe -Mn cycling manipulates the Ni, Cu, Zn, Co, Pb, Mo, V and Cr variations in the marine sediment. Adsorptions to Mn-oxyhydroxides can also enrich the trace metal in the marine deposition beds ([Tribovillard et al. 2006](#)).

In this study, the absolute concentration of the V varies by a factor of about 3 and normalised V/Th varies by a factor of about 2 across the Haymana profile ([Figure 14](#), [Figure 19](#)). The enriched V profile is limited up to +1 cm of the late Maastrichtian and the highest value is located at the K/Pg boundary clay. The V/Th profile has the highest peak at +460 cm in the P1b zone of the Danian besides the notable enrichments from the K/Pg boundary clay up to around +25 cm in the P α zone of the Danian; otherwise, the Danian profile is mostly depleted

while the Maastrichtian contains the most of the enriched values. However, the variation is not significant in these two sections. As the enrichment of the V in sediment indicates reducing conditions (Tribovillard et al. 2006) so, it could be inferred that the climatic and environmental stresses from the Deccan Trap eruption caused some degree of oxygen stress and reduced environment in the Haymana basin at the K/Pg boundary and immediately above and below. V is readily adsorbed to kaolinite, oxyhydroxides of Mn and Fe; under reduced conditions, the adsorption takes place faster and can increase the V enrichment in marine sediment (Tribovillard et al. 2006). As anoxia or reduced phase-induced enrichment is not obvious from any parallel observations so, it could be possible that mineralogical controls could enrich the V concentrations at the late Maastrichtian in the Haymana basin.

The As is a multivalent (with several oxidation states) element and for that reason As is a redox-sensitive trace element (Tribovillard 2020). The absolute concentration of the As varies by a factor of around 19 while the As/Th ratio varies by a factor of around 17 across the studied Haymana profile. The As/Th shows enrichment in the Danian with the highest value located at the K/Pg boundary clay and the second highest peak was observed at +460 cm in the P1b zone (Figure 19). The absolute concentration of As also follows more or less the same distribution pattern with the significant enrichment curve located between +60 cm to +110 cm in the P α zone of the Danian (Figure 14). This observation is suggestive of the existence of a reducing environment in the Haymana basin from the K/Pg boundary layer to the base of the early Danian and it perhaps was induced by the main phases of LIP eruptions at the Deccan hotspot around 66.03 Ma. Higher organic matter can also enhance the As concentrations (Tribovillard 2020) and therefore the enrichment curve in the Danian is also indicative of abundant OM from the opportunistic primary producers e.g., dinoflagellates of the Haymana

basin. In contrast, the low As concentration can be suggestive of a sulfidic deposition environment (Tribovillard 2020) which could also generate organic matter from the chemoautotrophy by sulphate-reducing microorganisms. Thus, the depleted concentration of As in the late Maastrichtian section of the sediment profile could be indicative of such anoxic to euxinic conditions in the western Tethys Ocean. However, the As, despite being a redox-sensitive element is not a consistent redox tracer and rather suggests the availability of reactive Fe in marine sediment beds; hence its enrichment reveals the presence of abundant reactive Fe that keeps the sulfide ions under control and prevents solubilization, migration and loss of As from the paleo settings proxy (Tribovillard 2020). The absolute concentration As of the studied sediment profile follows that of the U profile while the normalised As/Th is nearly parallel with that of the V/Th but in no situation there is any congruence with the Mo profile (Figure 14, Figure 19).

The redox tracers Cr likewise of U, V, and Co are strongly influenced by the detrital inputs, clay fractions besides mineralogical effects. The absolute concentration of Cr has followed the distribution pattern of V concentration having all the enriched values in the Maastrichtian mudstones of the Haymana basin and the highest value at the K/Pg boundary clay (Figure 14). The absolute Cr concentration varies by about a factor of 4 while the Cr/Th ratio varies by a factor of about 2 and the concerned distribution profile is nearly similar to the absolute Cr concentration profile (Figure 14). The highest value is at the K/Pg boundary and most of the enriched values are in the Maastrichtian while most of the depleted concentrations are at the Danian. Adsorption of the Cr to oxyhydroxides of Mn and Fe can enrich the sediments with Cr. Moreover, high OM can also transport the Cr into marine sediment which is reflected from the Cr enrichment spikes. In comparison under an extremely reduced environment such

euxinic water Cr is lost to overlaid water from the marine sediment by the sulfate-reducing bacteria (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Therefore, in the Haymana basin, the Cr enrichment in the Maastrichtian mudstones could be induced by producers e.g., dinoflagellates that preferentially bond with Cr with its OM and the post-K/Pg depleted values could point out euxinic phase across the early Danian – a proposition which is not corroborated by the behaviour of U and As in this study. Moreover, productivity from sulfate-reduction bacteria can also increase the OM that after bonding with Cr can induce enrichment spikes (Tribovillard et al. 2006).

The Cr enrichment in the Maastrichtian section could also suggest enhanced detrital flux while the Danian marl experienced the opposite. As the distal site in the Um section experienced excess humidity in the post-K/Pg (Keller 2014) therefore it is unlikely that the Haymana basin had lesser detrital flux during the early Danian. Clay mineral, ferromanganese mineral could also result in Cr enrichments in the Maastrichtian mudstones in the Haymana basin. In addition to these complexities, Cr burial occurs in anoxic and ferruginous water while Mo burial occurs best in euxinic water (Robbins et al. 2016). Thus, the Cr enrichment in this study reflects an anoxic environment while the Mo enrichment represents the euxinic environment of the depositional beds. For these complex interpretations, the application of Cr as a paleoredox proxy is limited and requires validations from the standard paleoredox proxies (Tribovillard et al. 2006).

It was observed that whereas U and V may be enriched in sediments under suboxic-anoxic conditions, Mo together with Ni, Cu is significantly enriched only under euxinic conditions (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Therefore, the absence of systematic variation of the Mo concentration suggests that changes in redox conditions could have a minor or no significant

influence on the trace element compositions of Haymana sediments at the K/Pg transition. The dissimilar trends of the redox-sensitive trace elements (e.g., V, Cr versus U, As) also fortifies the fact. The absence of significant correlations between Te/Th and Mo/Th, and between Te/Th and Tl/Th indicate that variations in redox state did not influence Te concentrations.

V.C. Interpretation of Paleoproductivity from Trace Element Proxies:

High Ni concentration has been used as a tracer of massive volcanism e.g., Siberian Trap during the P/T mass extinction ([Brookfield et al. 2021](#); [Rampino et al. 2017](#)). However, other studies have used Ni concentrations in sediments as a proxy for paleoproductivity (e.g. [Tribovillard et al. 2006](#)). In this study, in the Maastrichtian part of the sedimentary profile, Ni has a larger concentration range with the highest concentration at the K/Pg boundary layer. The extreme enrichment of Ni and high Ni/Th of the KPg boundary clay likely reflects an extraterrestrial component at this level. The post-K/Pg saw a high decline both in the absolute concentration of Ni and Ni/Th ([Figure 14](#), [Figure 19](#)). The absolute concentration of Ni varies by about a factor of 10 while after normalisation the ratio (Ni/Th) varies by about a factor of 4 across this profile. Excluding the K/Pg boundary clay, Ni/Th varies only by a factor of about 2, suggesting that volcanism and variations in paleoproductivity had a minor influence on Ni concentrations, which because of the similarity in the Ni and Th profiles, varies largely because of differences in the carbonate content of the sediments, and is therefore lower in the early Danian.

It appears that the second phase of the Deccan Trap LIP was concomitant with the highest Ni contents of the Haymana sediment profile but the final eruption phase had witnessed Ni

depletion. But, from the different P/Tr sedimentary records, it is also postulated that normalised Ni-enrichment by volcanism is not a universal truth (Regelous et al. 2020). Other than volcanic processes organisms can also control the Ni distribution which behaves as a nutrient-type element in seawater (Brookfield et al. 2021; Chester & Jickells 2012). During the higher productivity, their scavenging from seawater and formation of Ni-organic matter (organometallic or OM) complex causes Ni-enrichment of the sediment while the decay of their body removes the Ni to pore water and can induce Ni-depletion in marine sediment (Chester & Jickells 2012; Tribovillard et al. 2006). Therefore, the mass extinction of the marine primary producers at the K/Pg boundary and the post-K/Pg stress by the third phase of eruption at the Deccan Trap LIP (Keller 2014; Keller et al. 2018; Keller et al. 2016) could hinder the recovery of the phytoplankton and decline the Ni concentration in the Haymana basin during the Danian. Moreover, under moderate reducing conditions sediment becomes depleted in Ni (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Therefore, the local scale redox state during the Danian could also influence the Ni variation herein.

Zn and Cd are also enriched in the volcanogenic aerosol likewise Ni but productivity also controls their concentration (Regelous et al. 2020). Under oxic conditions, they behave like nutrient-type elements with higher productivity resulting in their depletion in seawater and enriching of the sediment (Tribovillard et al. 2006). The post-K/Pg rise of the normalised Zn and Cd concentration with the highest value at +460 cm of the Danian (P1b zone) indicates a higher productivity scenario which is contradictory to the Ni/Th distribution but the Sb/Th pattern is similar to the normalised Zn and Cd variations. The highest absolute concentration of Zn is observed at the K/Pg boundary layer while the highest range of Cd concentration is located from the K/Pg boundary clay to +380 cm in the P1b zone of the early Danian. The

absolute Zn concentration varies by a factor of around 3 whereas the absolute Cd concentration varies by a factor of around 8 (Figure 14). The normalised Zn/Th varies by a factor of 2 while the Cd/Th varies by a factor of 1 across the sediment profile (Figure 19). After decay, the Zn is released to pore water from the OM complex and under the reducing phase they can be incorporated into pyrite (Tribovillard et al. 2006). But these events result in Zn depletion in the sediment which is opposite to the observed Zn profile in the early Danian section of the Haymana basin. The Cd also behave similar way however under mild to strong reducing conditions, in the presence of H₂S, the marine sediments can be enriched with Cd (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Moreover, Cd enrichment is also controlled by CO₃²⁻ and therefore in the Haymana sediment profile, the variation in concentration of Cd and Sr is similar with more enrichment in the post-K/Pg sediment profile due to their higher carbonate content. It may be possible that the Zn distribution was controlled more by the volcanic eruption from the Deccan Trap while the local redox phase by sulfate-reducing bacteria had controlled the Cd concentrations. Even so, the normalised concentration of Zn, Cd and Sb of the Haymana profile reflect stresses on productivity in late Maastrichtian.

Cu and Ba are also used as productivity tracers. In the Haymana basin, the Cu concentrations declined in the early Danian marl while for Ba the higher and lower values are spread across the profile although some of the highest enriched values are observed in the Maastrichtian sediment profile. Overall, the absolute concentration of Cu varies by a factor of around 3 whereas that of Ba varies by a factor of about 65 (Figure 14). The most enriched Cu concentration is located at the K/Pg boundary and the same is observed for the Ba.

Primary production and redox state affect the Cu likewise that of the Ni, Zn and Cd (Tribovillard 2021) and hence the reduction in primary productivity and subsequent drop in OM could be

the reason for the decline in Cu concentration in the post-K/Pg and the pre-K/Pg profile of the Haymana sediment. A high flux of OM could bring Cu into the marine sediment, together with the increase in carbonate content but as the mechanism did not influence the Cd and Zn profile therefore it cannot be inferred that the late Maastrichtian of the Haymana basin was more productive than the early Danian. In modern times preferential uptake of Cu by the members of the Chrysophyta and Bacillariophyta has been reported (Zhang et al. 2022). Therefore, it could be possible that Cu was preferentially uptaken by any specific group of diatoms in the shallow western Tethys Ocean during the k/Pg and the diatom OM bond with Cu enriched the late Maastrichtian Haymana profile.

The absolute concentration of Ba herein is almost similar to the distribution pattern of Mo absolute concentration (Figure 14). But unlike the Mo, the Ba was not regulated by extraterrestrial/celestial inputs during the K/Pg event but linked with lithology. Since Ba is depleted in chondritic meteorites relative to the Earth's crust, high Ba in the K/Pg boundary clay may reflect high Ba concentrations in the target rocks close to the Chicxulub crater. The Ni and Ba concentrations from the K/Pg boundary clay in sites in India are much lower than the values of the Haymana basin however, those values from the K/Pg boundary locations in Italy (Bhandari et al. 1993) are somewhat closer to the concentration ranges of the Haymana basin (Figure 20).

Nevertheless, some factors are also crucial in deciphering the Ba concentration in marine environments. Besides the detrital control, the high primary productivity derived OM can also enrich the Ba in marine sediments and under euxinic conditions marine sediment is depleted with Ba. However, early diagenesis can enrich the sediment in the absence of high surface water productivity. As the sulfate-reducing environment also can produce OM so interpreting

Ba is not reliable in highly productive environments and thus, the application of Ba as a paleoproductivity proxy is restricted to low to moderate marine productivity (Tribovillard et al. 2006). Since the paleo bathymetry of the Haymana basin was 400 m (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019) therefore, it can be assumed that the western Tethys in the Haymana basin regained productivity in the Maastrichtian that lay in between the first and second eruption pulse of the Deccan LIP. Moreover, the concomitant dinocyst profile near the K/Pg boundary is also indicative of the high biomass of the dinocyst (Figure 21). For these reasons, the complex behaviour of the Ba concentration across the Haymana basin is difficult to interpret.

V.C.1. Primary Production at K/Pg Transition:

The K/Pg mass extinction eliminated more than 90% of the producers secreting the carbonate shell at the base of the marine food web (Hull et al. 2020; Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019; Keller et al. 2018) although, this observation does not corroborate the enrichment profile of the productivity tracers at post-K/Pg sediment repository herein (Figure 14, Figure 19). In the marine environment other than the carbonate-secreting phytoplankton, the organic-walled chlorophyllous microorganisms i.e. dinoflagellate, also control the primary productions. The algal biomarker analysis of the K/Pg sediment repository from the mid-Waipara River section, North Canterbury, New Zealand determined an increase in warm water-dwelling marine dinoflagellate species, *Trithyrodinium evittii* and it is in concomitant with within planktonic foraminiferal biozone P0. After a transient drop with the domination cold water-dwelling dinoflagellate *Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum* (corresponded with P α foraminifera biozone), the peak of *Trithyrodinium evittii* reappeared again at the basal Paleogene (P1a-c) (Figure 21) (de Oca et al. 2023; Taylor et al. 2018). This productivity regime of the SW Pacific has been reported from other K/Pg sites e.g. Brazos River bed, (Vellekoop et al. 2014), Maastrichtian to

Danian transgression in north Patagonia (Guler et al. 2019), El Haria Formation near El Kef K/Pg stratotype section, Tunisia (Vellekoop et al. 2015). In the Okçular section of the Mudurnu–Göynük basin in NW Turkey representing the southwestern Tethys Ocean, the warm-tolerant dinocyst concentration across the K-Pg boundary, from the upper Maastrichtian to the lower Danian increased by about 7 fold (Figure 21) (Vellekoop et al. 2017).

Figure 21: (A) Dinoflagellate assemblages in Waipara estuary (Modified from (de Oca et al. 2023; Taylor et al. 2018)). (B) Dinoflagellate assemblages in Mudurnu–Göynük basin during the K/Pg transition. (Modified from (Vellekoop et al. 2017)). The red dashed line indicates the K/Pg boundary layer.

Those observations are in view that the organic-walled disaster-tolerant dinoflagellates occupied the niche of carbonate-secreting nanoplanktons by means of heterotrophy and mixotrophy (Gibbs et al. 2020) and utilised the nutrients including trace elements in the course of its primary production. It was noted that the initial increase in *T. evittii* with > 6% of the assemblage was observed directly below the K/Pg boundary whereas directly above the K/Pg

boundary the dinocyst assemblage increased up to 18% before the transitional decline at the mid-Waipara River bed (Taylor et al. 2018) whereas in the western Tethys, there was about 35% rise in lower-latitude dwelling dinocyst (Hexaperidinioids: *Senegalinium* and *Cerodinium*) assemblage at P0, and after the transient cool phase (impact winter) drop, their assemblage again rose to about 35% (Vellekoop et al. 2017). The capacity of the autotrophic phytoplankton to adopt heterotrophy and mixotrophy allows them to recover from the K/Pg extinction stress with the recolonisation of the cyanobacteria and reestablishment of the marine food web (Gibbs et al. 2020).

The findings validate that the fluctuation of the concentration of some trace elements at the Haymana basin during the K/Pg could also be linked with productivity. The trace element enrichment and depletion at the upsection from the K/Pg boundary onwards in the Haymana basin, therefore, could be linked with the proliferation of the Hexaperidinioids and/or *Trithyrodinium evittii* in the western Tethys water. The lesser distributional ranges of the trace element concentration at the distal sections of the late Maastrichtian profile in this study could be linked with the reduction in warm water dwelling dinocyst blooms, lesser temperature gradient and perhaps weaker biological pump and in western Tethys Ocean. Add to these observations, from the metalloenzymes studies it has been found that the order of biological utilization of trace elements usually follows the pattern Fe >> Zn > Mn >> Mo, Co, Cu >> Ni > V (Robbins et al. 2016). Therefore, it could also be possible that it was the biological requirements of the phytoplanktons and cyanobacteria that made the Haymana basin enriched in terms of Zn, and Cd over Ni. The relatively higher enrichment of Zn and Cr over Ni from the riverine bed at mid-Waipara River, New Zealand during the K/Pg boundary (Taylor et al. 2018) reflected the similar behaviours of the trace elements in connection with

productivity in the aquatic environment.

The abundance of the mixotrophs and heterotrophs thus hinders the simplified interpretation of the trace elemental concentration in the Haymana basin in connection with productivity as despite the declined nanoplankton productivity, the organic-walled dinoflagellate did not suffer from the stress of the K/Pg mass extinction and became a more important primary producer at the early Paleogene ([de Oca et al. 2023](#); [Vellekoop et al. 2017](#)).

V.D. Hg Enrichment:

Mercury enrichments in sediments have been widely used as a proxy for volcanic input since Hg is enriched in volcanic gas and can be transported far from the site of volcanism ([Grasby et al. 2019](#)). The Hg enrichment in the sedimentary profile is not necessarily indicative of LIP eruptions but may be influenced by other factors including redox conditions, organic matter flux, and clay mineral content ([Shen et al. 2020](#)). In this study Hg concentration was more enriched in the late Maastrichtian section of the Haymana basin with the highest value at -230 cm however the enrichment has no systemic distribution as intermittent peaks were observed throughout the Maastrichtian of the sampled profile with the oldest peak at -740 cm to -730 cm ([Figure 13](#)). The Danian section has rather depleted concentrations with one moderately enriched peak between +40 cm to +80 cm of the P α zone, and another at +230 cm of the P1b zone while the least concentration is at +460 cm of the P1b zone. It has to be noted that the Hg concentration at 0 cm (the K/Pg boundary clay) is absent in this work because not enough sample was available for analysis.

The normalised Hg concentration (Hg/Th) displays both higher and lower values in the late Maastrichtian mudstones with a broad peak in the latest Maastrichtian (-400 cm to -100 cm)

which have two noted enriched excursions at -300 cm and from -240 cm to -230 cm ([Figure 19](#)). In the early Danian marls, +3 cm and +9 cm of the P0 zone represent intense depletion while there is a significant enrichment at +7 cm of the P0 zone. The next enrichment peak is observed at +280 cm in the P1b zone of the Danian. However, the Hg/Th varies by only a factor of 2 in both the upper Maastrichtian and lower Danian profiles ([Figure 19](#)). This suggests that the contribution of volcanism to the Hg contents of Haymana sediments was minor. There is also no significant correlation between Hg/Th and Te/Th ([Figure 22](#)). The similarity in the Hg and Th profiles indicates that the generally lower Hg concentrations in the Danian sediments is at least partly due to their higher carbonate contents.

As Hg is a redox-sensitive element, under a reduced environment sediments can be enriched with Hg ([Shen et al. 2020](#)). But the concomitant Mo/Th, As/Th and V/Th ([Figure 19](#)) do not strongly support redox control on the intermittent enrichment spikes of the Hg/Th profile in the Maastrichtian mudstones except for the one around -760 cm to -770 cm; in the Danian enrichment curve immediate to the post-K/Pg is somewhat analogous to As/Th and V/Th profile but there Hg depletions are also located.

The Hg can also be enriched by primary production ([Gehrke et al. 2009](#)), especially as a result of adsorption onto organic material. Although between -800 cm to -700 cm and sediment profile near the K/Pg boundary clay, the concomitant productivity tracers like Zn/Th, Ni/Th and Cd/Th ([Figure 19](#)) support the notion but in other places, the Hg/Th distribution pattern is not corroborated by the other normalised trace element ratio. Mercury's strong association with organic compounds, sulfide and clay minerals hinders the interpretation of Hg spikes under a reducing environment ([Regelous et al. 2020](#); [Sanei et al. 2012](#)). The early Danian proliferation of organic-walled primary producers and bacteria ([de Oca et al. 2023](#); [Gibbs et al.](#)

2020) specifically from the K/Pg boundary onwards, the abundant diatoms in the pre-K/Pg profile (Bergstresser & Krebs 1983; Chambers 1997) could have increased OM bond with Hg in Tethys water column. Under the reduction phase, these OM could transport the Hg into marine sediment whereas during the intermittent oxic points, the Hg could be removed to the overlying pore water and resulted in Hg depletion in the Haymana sediment. However, the negative correlations of Hg/Te with the other trace element ratios (Figure 22) suggest that Hg/Th in the Haymana basin was not promoted by the factors that control the Mo, V, Ni, Zn, Cd, Tl, and Sb. Total organic carbon (TOC) contents of the Haymana sediments were low (<0.2 %) and therefore difficult to measure precisely, but low TOC contents suggest that variations in TOC are unlikely to control Hg contents.

The Hg/Th variations have irregular enrichment across the Haymana profile; as the volcanic eruptions in Deccan Trap flood basalt had three to four eruption phases so the post-K/Pg spikes could relate to those LIP eruptions. The Hg spikes at the K/Pg boundary layer reflect a high variability range from 46.6 to 576 µg/kg (Grasby et al. 2019) and therefore, the Hg concentrations in the Haymana basin are in agreement with the previously observed Hg range. However, the volcanic phases of the Deccan are thought to have each lasted approximately 100 kyrs, and therefore longer than the spikes in Hg enrichment observed at Haymana. In addition, the Hg enrichment in the Maastrichtian section of the Haymana profile occurred during the ~1.5 Ma hiatus phase of the Deccan Trap when the temperature was reduced by ~5°C. The OM-bond of the Hg driven by disaster-tolerant primary production could be a reason for such inconsistent distribution of Hg. The Hg can also be introduced to sediment from hydrothermal vents, however since the Haymana basin depth was within 400 m, this possibility could be ruled out and the presence of any nearby submarine volcanoes is

not known yet. Alternatively, the short-period 'spikes' in Hg observed in Haymana sediments could result from single large eruptions from the convergent plate margin volcanoes located within a few hundred kilometers of the Haymana Basin to the southeast ([Figure 8](#)). As the Hg is easily mobilised during post-depositional alteration (secondary diagenesis) ([Charbonnier et al. 2020](#); [Regelous et al. 2020](#)) hence this alteration deters from using it as a reliable volcanic tracer. Although widespread deposition of Hg from volcanogenic aerosol to marine sediment makes it a proxy of the past flood basalt eruptions nevertheless with the growing number of case studies it has been showing limitations. In the Haymana section, there is no indication that the observed relatively small variations in Hg content or Hg/Th ratio are related to Deccan volcanism.

	Te/Th	Cd/Th	Mo/Th	V/Th	Zn/Th	Ni/Th	Tl/Th	Mo/Th	Sb/Th	Hg/Th
Te/Th		0.50955	0.27056	0.32796	0.16437	0.098696	0.1647	0.27056	0.33821	-0.081323
Cd/Th	0.50955		0.12503	0.30507	0.5747	-0.28159	0.56905	0.12503	0.33601	-0.090207
Mo/Th	0.27056	0.12503		0.18866	0.13151	0.75976	0.3949	1	0.83715	-0.45704
V/Th	0.32796	0.30507	0.18866		0.60084	0.401	0.12809	0.18866	0.42844	-0.095666
Zn/Th	0.16437	0.5747	0.13151	0.60084		-0.052695	0.48738	0.13151	0.48996	-0.082596
Ni/Th	0.098696	-0.28159	0.75976	0.401	-0.052695		0.023144	0.75976	0.62701	-0.37237
Tl/Th	0.1647	0.56905	0.3949	0.12809	0.48738	0.023144		0.3949	0.39231	-0.2274
Mo/Th	0.27056	0.12503	1	0.18866	0.13151	0.75976	0.3949		0.83715	-0.45704
Sb/Th	0.33821	0.33601	0.83715	0.42844	0.48996	0.62701	0.39231	0.83715		-0.38127
Hg/Th	-0.081323	-0.090207	-0.45704	-0.095666	-0.082596	-0.37237	-0.2274	-0.45704	-0.38127	

Figure 22: Correlation between Th normalised Hg, Cd, Mo, V, Zn, Ni, Tl and Th normalised Te. Inset table shows correlation matrix.

V.E. Te Enrichment:

The chalcophile element tellurium was discovered in 1782, by Franz-Joseph Mueller von Reichenstein and in nature, it can be found in gold ore as calaverite (AuTe_2), sylvanite (AgAuTe_4) and nagyagite [$\text{AuPb}(\text{Sb}, \text{Bi})\text{Te}_{2-3}\text{S}_6$] (Presentato et al. 2016). The Te is one of the least abundant elements in the Earth's crust and ocean water despite having a higher abundance in the cosmos than the other elements with an atomic number of over 40 (Hein et al. 2003). Due to the volatility of Te, a large fraction of the Earth's initial inventory of Te was lost during accretion, and the bulk of the remaining Te is located in the Earth's core. Perhaps for being not a biologically essential element its biogeochemical properties are not studied well. The average Te concentration in the earth's crust is around 0.027 ppm (Ramos-Ruiz et al. 2016). The subduction of Te-rich oceanic crust (ferromanganese oxyhydroxide [Fe-Mn] crusts, shale, and pelagic sediments) boosts higher Te content in the mantle than the crust (Zhang et al. 2023). In the aquatic environment, the prominent oxidation states of Te are tellurate (TeO_4^{2-} [(+6), Te^{VI}]), tellurite (TeO_3^{2-} [(+4), Te^{IV}]), and elemental Te^0 (0) (Ramos-Ruiz et al. 2016) (Figure 23). Thermodynamically Te^{IV} is more stable and lesser abundant than Te^{VI} in ocean (Hein et al. 2003).

Figure 23: Chemical structures of prominent Te-oxyanions – (1) Tellurate [Te^{VI}], (2) Tellurite [Te^{IV}].

As the Te is enriched in volcanic aerosol compared to the magma relative to all other volatile chalcophile elements except S (i.e. highly degassed, (Zelenski et al. 2014)), it could be a

potential tracer of paleovolcanism (Regelous et al. 2020). Submarine volcanogenic hydrothermal activities linked with local intraplate volcanism of the late Miocene had enriched the Te concentrations in the Central Indian Ocean Basin (Zhang et al. 2023). In this study, the absolute concentration of the Te range in the Haymana basin varies by a factor of around 3 whereas the Te/Th ratio varies by a factor of about 2. The pre-K/Pg Te concentration range is wider having both the low and high values although intermittent Te enrichment is also observed across the early Danian profile (Figure 13). In the Danian marls, immediately above the K/Pg boundary, Te concentration decreases and then enrichment peaks are observed at +40 cm to +50 cm of the P α zone, +230 cm to +240 cm of the P1b zone, and +340 cm of the P1b zone. The absence of any gradual pattern in this sediment profile is one of the hindrances in commenting on the controls of Te. The lower Te concentrations in the Danian are at least partly due to the higher carbonate content of these sediments, as indicated by a broad positive correlation between Te and Th. The normalised Te/Th profile, which is unaffected by carbonate content, indicates that Te/Th began to increase from the late Maastrichtian (above -200 cm) and the highest value is noted at +15 cm in the P0 zone of the early Danian (Figure 19). After a decrease in the Pa zone, the Te/Th ratio again continues to increase into the P1a and P1b zones of the early Danian. These variations are at least consistent with U-Pb zircon ages for the Deccan (Schoene et al. 2019), which indicate a pulse of Deccan volcanism immediately before the K/Pg in the latest Maastrichtian, and a second pulse approximately 100 kyr after the K/Pg (Figure 4).

The higher Te/Th ratio at the K/Pg boundary clay, pre-K/Pg up to -60 cm of the Maastrichtian, and post-K/Pg depositions are not apparently due to lithological and mineralogical variations. Hydrothermal pyrite can contain high amounts of Te (Regelous et al. 2020) but the presence of

pyrites has not been known yet from this section of the Haymana basin.

High ferromanganese oxyhydroxide (Fe-Mn-OOH) nodules in sediment can contain high Te alongside the high concentrations of REE, Tl, and paleo-redox-sensitive elements e.g., Mo (Hein et al. 2003; Regelous et al. 2020). But in the Haymana sediment profile, Fe-Mn driven enrichment of Te is not associated with the concentrations of the REEs and Mo (Figure 14). Moreover, Fe-Mn precipitates in cold deep water whereas the K/Pg transition experienced intense high-temperature stress globally (Keller et al. 2018) and the Haymana paleo bathymetry is estimated as 400 m (Karabeyoğlu et al. 2019) which except for some partial seasonal thermocline is not an ideal depth for the confluence of any concomitant deep cold water current (Lalli & Parsons 1997). In addition, it is considered that oxidation of Te^{4+} to Te^{6+} on the Fe-Mn-OOH surface results in high enrichment of Te (Hein et al. 2003) but during the K/Pg transition phase, the Haymana basin was most likely under the influence of a somewhat reducing environment as the paleoredox tracers suggest (Figure 14). Therefore, it seems that Fe-Mn-OOH could not be a reason for Te enrichments in the western Tethys Ocean water of the Haymana basin. The enrichment profile Sb/Th and Tl/Th has little visual similarity with the Te/Th in the early Danian (Figure 19) but because of the dissimilarity with other parallel REEs profiles, it is unlikely that a phosphatic phase had controlled the Te enrichment in the early Danian section as the phosphate phase would also enrich the REE concentrations in marine sediment (Regelous et al. 2020).

The Hg and Te contained in the coal bed of the Siberian basin were considered to enrich the Hg and Te content at the LPE sediment with explosive gas (CO_2 , CH_4) release during metamorphism (Bullock et al. 2019; Regelous et al. 2020). Add to this reflection it is found that Te precipitation and enrichment occurred by microbial actions in the pyrite bed of the

Carboniferous paleo-oil reservoirs during the degradation of the oil in South Central Britain (Parnell et al. 2015) but here in the Haymana basin such possibilities have no report yet and are therefore excluded from consideration.

V.E.1. Te Biogeochemistry and Te Enrichment:

As referred earlier Te^{VI} and Te^{IV} are two dominant oxidation states (oxyanions) of Te in water. More than a hundred strains of bacteria that are potentially capable of reducing the Te-oxyanions have been identified in Antarctica (Arenas et al. 2014; Missen et al. 2020). Microbial bioreduction of Te oxyanions comprises of two pathways: bioprecipitation (biomineralization) and biovolatilisation. The bioprecipitation involves in formation of Te^0 nanoparticles possibly using an NADH-dependent pathway in the presence of S-adenosyl-methionine (SAM), whereas biovolatilisation involves in formation of alkylated volatile organotellurium compounds e.g., $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Te}$ as SAM bind to a telluro-methylase enzyme (TehB) in this phase (Gil-Díaz et al. 2019; Missen et al. 2020). The biooxidation (bioleaching) on the other hand involves oxidising of Te^0 by thiobacillus-like microbial oxidisers and releasing the soluble telluride (Te oxyanions) from the sludge to overlying water in cost of Te toxicity (Missen et al. 2020) and results in Te depletion in the underlying marine sediment. However, the Te biogeochemical cycle is mostly hypothetical and envisaged from the well-studied Se biogeochemistry cycle as Te is very similar to Se over the other trace elements (Missen et al. 2020). The entire pathways can be expressed in the equations (unbalanced) that are mentioned in the following box note-1:

Box Note - 1

Bioprecipitation: $\text{TeO}_3^{2-} (aq) \leftrightarrow \text{Te}^0 (i)$

Biovolatilisation: $\text{TeO}_3^{2-} (aq) \leftrightarrow (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Te}(g)$

Biooxidation: $\text{Te}^0 \leftrightarrow \text{Te}(s)$

The majority of Te-reducing microorganisms are gram (-ve) bacteria and the rest belong to gram (+ve) bacteria, alpha-proteobacteria and fungi (Missen et al. 2020; Presentato et al. 2016). Microorganisms like *Bacillus selenitireducens*, *Sulfurospirillum barnesii*, *Desulfovibrio desulfuricans*, *Rhodococcus aetherivorans* are capable of reducing oxyanions of Te (Te^{IV} and Te^{VI}) to insoluble Te^0 nanoparticles in sulfur-free anoxic water and precipitate the Te^0 both intracellularly and extracellularly (cytoplasm and cell membrane) which favours Te enrichment in marine sediment (Presentato et al. 2016; Ramos-Ruiz et al. 2016). This organotellurium matrix is more stable than Te-O, Te-H or Te-Te bonds. Further metabolic reduction of organotellurium could generate H_2Te which afterwards of methylation either can give rise to volatile dimethyl telluride $[(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Te}]$ or ionic $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Te}^+$ as evident from the microbial metabolic pathway of Se (Figure 24) (Ba et al. 2010; Missen et al. 2020).

Figure 24: Hypothetical Te metabolic pathway schemes of super microbes. (Modified from (Missen et al. 2020)).

Therefore, during the post-K/Pg anoxia, microbial respiration of toxic Te-oxyanions could result in the Te enrichments in the Danian marl of the Haymana basin which were nearly contemporaneous with the stresses of the second and third phases of the Deccan trap volcanic eruptions. On the other hand, the depleted values across the Haymana profile could be indicative of the release of the Te-oxyanions to the Tethys Ocean in the absence of anoxia. However, the established paleoredox trace elements do not show uniformity in delineating the redox condition across the Haymana profile ([Figure 14](#), [Figure 19](#)) and thus, it is not possible to determine how the anoxia in the western Tethys Ocean regulated the Te concentration during the late Maastrichtian to the early Danian. Although the diatom taxa counting in the upper Maastrichtian from the western interior of the United States and Antarctic sediment ([Bergstresser & Krebs 1983](#); [Chambers 1997](#)) could relate to the recovery of oxygen concentration from the stress of 1st Deccan trap eruption, ~67.5 Ma but it has to be noted that the diatoms were less affected than the nanoplanktons during K/Pg events because of their ability to produce resting spores in harsh environments ([Chambers 1997](#)).

From the concentrations of the paleoproductivity signifying parallel trace elements except for the Ni, it is apparent that productivity in the post-K/Pg section was rather high ([Figure 14](#), [Figure 19](#)). The post-K/Pg marine food web was dominated by autotrophic and heterotrophic productivity of the microbial members for ~2 Myrs ([Gibbs et al. 2020](#)). Moreover, the dinoflagellate profiles in the upper Maastrichtian and lower Danian also pointed out extensive concurrent productivity even in stressful environments in some previous studies ([Brinkhuis et al. 1998](#)). Historical records also revealed phytoplankton blooms linked with red tides resulted in the Te enrichment in the East China Sea sediment repository ([Gil-Díaz et al. 2019](#)). Therefore, the possibility of productivity-related control on Te concentration in the Hayman sediment profile cannot be ruled out.

On the other hand, despite the near parallelism in the absolute concentration of Hg and Te, the Hg/Th and Te/Th variations of the Haymana basin are occasionally analogous ([Figure 19](#)). The closest proximities of the two profiles have been observed at -1 cm and +1 cm of the sediment although the values of the Hg at (the K/Pg boundary) and -190 cm are unavailable. Moreover, the Te/Th has a narrowly negative correlation with the Hg/Th ([Figure 22](#)) and it can be assumed that the negative correlation could be overcome if the two Hg values including the one at the K/Pg boundary were available.

The Te enrichment in the late Neoproterozoic (Ediacaran) black shales (Gwna Group, UK) is indicative of increased continental weathering besides higher biological activity like primary production ([Armstrong et al. 2018](#)). As the post-K/Pg is reported to witness high acid rain ([Keller 2014](#)) therefore the post-K/Pg high Te/Th ratios could also be suggestive of increased terrigenous sediment flux to the Haymana basin, and subsequent enhanced primary production by the microbes and dinoflagellates. The contemporaneous dinoflagellate profile ([Vellekoop et al. 2017](#)) of abundant warm- and salinity-tolerant dinoflagellate Hexaperidinioids in the Mudurnu–Göynük basin of the south-west Tethys Ocean ([Figure 21](#)) reveal an enhanced primary production regime in the Tethys Ocean near the Haymana basin during the K/Pg transition. Although the Neoproterozoic black shales were deposited in an anoxic environment, but the trace elements markers discussed above (U, Mo, Tl) suggest limited oxygen deficiency stress across the post-K/Pg Haymana basin.

V.E.2. Deccan Trap Volcanism and Te Enrichment:

Across the K/Pg boundary clay (-1 cm and +1 cm) Hg/Th and Te/Th are the same. Moreover, both in the late Maastrichtian and the early Danian normalised concentration of Hg and Te

varies by about a factor of 2 and correspondingly for the entire Haymana sedimentary profile, the increment of Te/Th and Hg/Th appears to be the same (about a factor of 2). The nearness of the enrichment trends between the Hg/Th and Te/Th immediately at the pre-K/Pg boundary (-1 cm) and post-K/Pg boundary (+1 cm) ([Figure 19](#)) and both in the pre-K/Pg and post-K/Pg profile is indicative of the likewise source of Hg and Te in the Haymana basin. As volcanic gas is highly enriched in Te (10^6 - 10^7) likewise the Hg ([Zelenski et al. 2014](#)) hence LIP eruption could also enrich the Te concentration in the Haymana basin. Celestial events like bolide impact could generate such similarity only in the K/Pg boundary clay whereas the coexisting Deccan Trap eruption phases could induce the Te enrichment periodically across the K/Pg transition during the period 65.5 to 66.5 Ma, when the Deccan volcanism was active.

Volcanic eruptions, quiescent degassing (e.g. fumaroles), or hydrothermal activity release volatile Te [e.g. H_2Te (g)] and therefore are important sources of Te. For instance, Te varies from 10–1000 mg/kg in volcanogenic sulphur; fumaroles of Avacha volcano in Kamchatka, Russia hold 15.9 mg/kg Te. Fumarolic deposits in Vulcao island, Italy and Vatu koula, Fiji also contain Te. The deep-sea black smoker sulfide and volcanogenic sulfide are more enriched with Te over the earth's crust ([Gil-Díaz et al. 2019](#)). A high amount of Te had been detected from the Spitsbergen sediment profile that was concurrent with the Siberian Trap at the P/T mass extinction phase ([Regelous et al. 2020](#)). Volcanic aerosol contains highly volatile Te halide (F, Cl) or hydride ([Moune et al. 2006](#)) which is deposited only in the coolest parts of volcanic gas collection equipment ([Regelous et al. 2020](#); [Zelenski et al. 2014](#)). The mean magma extrusion rate increased after the K/Pg ([Schoene et al. 2019](#); [Sprain et al. 2019](#)) and henceforth, it could be possible that the high-temperature stress from the main eruption pulses of the Deccan Trap LIP (with a rise of $\sim 5^\circ\text{C}$) kept the western Tethys water of the Haymana basin mostly warm

during the lower Danian and therefore, the parallel Te (and Hg) concentrations show sign of depletion despite the initial enrichment spikes up to few meters above the K/Pg boundary (Figure 19). The atmospheric residence time of volcanic Te is still unknown but Te can be distributed over several thousands of kilometres during massive flood basalt eruptions (Regelous et al. 2020). Therefore, the Te-rich aerosol of the Deccan Trap eruptions potentially regulated Te distributions in the Haymana basin (Figure 25).

The relative gradual increase in Te/Th in the Maastrichtian from around -110 cm towards the K/Pg boundary clay could signify the temperature and oxygen stress as the onset of the second phase of the Deccan Trap eruption. The Te/Th correlations with some other normalised trace elements (Figure 22) are either weakly positive (e.g. Cd/Th with Te/Th) or have none (e.g. Ni/Th with Te/Th). This correlation suggests that in the Haymana basin source and controls of trace elements Mo, V, Ni, Zn, Cd, Tl, and Sb possibly did not influence Te concentration. In other words, the Te did not vary significantly with the redox and productivity state of the Haymana basin during the late Maastrichtian to early Danian transition. Moreover, the average concentration of Te and Th in average continental crust is 27 ppb and 5.6 ppm, so the average Te/Th in average continental crust is 4.8 (ppb/ppm). All of the measured Te/Th values in the sampled section of the Haymana basin are higher (23.98-10.51) than this average crustal ratio and therefore, so all samples of the Haymana basin could potentially contain a volcanic Te component of more than 50%.

The third phase of the Deccan Trap flood basalt eruption was identified as the boundary between P α and P1a biozone and therefore corresponds with +180 cm of the Haymana sediment profile. The Te/Th value in Haymana again shows re-enrichment above this boundary perhaps for the same reason. Previous observation found background Te signal (~

1 ppb) in the absence of volcanism (Baumann et al. 2023) but in this present work, the Te concentration did not show any such reduction closer to the crustal values of Te. Besides the voluminous volcanisms, other environmental mechanisms also control the concentrations of these trace elements in the marine sediment repositories. Henceforth, it could be possible that after the recovery of Deccan Trap phase-2 driven oxygen minima, microbial oxidation of Te^0 resulted in Te depletion in the western Tethys Ocean. Alternatively, afterwards the main Deccan Trap volcanism stress, the reduction in primary production and organic matter could not allow the bioprecipitation of Te oxyanions into the Haymana basin sediment from +30 cm to around +220 cm of the Danian segment. However, the concomitant dinoflagellate profile (Figure 21) reflected abundant organic matter in ocean water globally (de Oca et al. 2023; Taylor et al. 2018; Vellekoop et al. 2015; Vellekoop et al. 2017). The continuation of the fluctuating enrichment trend from +300 cm of the Danian (P1b zone) could be linked with the fourth phase of the Deccan Trap LIP eruption. It has been recorded that submarine volcanogenic hydrothermal activities linked with local intraplate volcanism of the late Miocene had enriched the Te concentrations in the Central Indian Ocean Basin (Zhang et al. 2023). Therefore, some Te in the Haymana sediment profile could emanate from the eruptions from the subduction zone volcanoes located on the convergent plate margin of the African and Eurasian plates within a few hundred kilometers of the Haymana Basin to the southeast (Figure 8). However, this was likely in the form of a 'background' volcanic Te input, since the intensity of subduction zone volcanism is unlikely to change over 100 kyr to 1 myr timescales.

Figure 25: The normalised Hg and Te ratio of the Haymana basin from this study and the concurrent Deccan Trap LIP eruption phases (P) (Modified from (Schoene et al. 2019)). Red dashed horizontal line represents the K/Pg boundary layer contemporary to P-2 eruption, and magenta dashed line indicates the possible P-3 eruption and the concomitant Hg/Th and Te/Th profile of the Haymana basin.

V.F. Influence of Deccan Trap Volcanic Emissions on Haymana Basin at K/Pg Transition:

The similar variations of Hg/Th and Te/Th ratios along with normalised concentrations of some other trace elements in the Haymana basin in and around the K/Pg boundary clay ([Figure 19](#), [Figure 25](#)) implies the occurrence of a massive disturbance in the marine ecosystem in the Tethys Ocean water overlying the Haymana basin during the late Maastrichtian to the early Danian transition that was contemporaneous with the Chicxulub bolide impact and the main phase of the Deccan Trap flood basalt event. The intermittent enrichment acmes of the normalised elemental ratios across the studied sediment profile hinder the consideration of bolide impact-induced anomalies in most of the corresponding trace element profiles of the Haymana basin.

In the Haymana basin, the high Te/Th ratios, besides immediately above the K/Pg boundary clay (P0 zone) were also observed immediately (P0 zone) above the K/Pg boundary, around +200 cm in P1a zone and further up in the P1b zone ([Figure 14](#)) and these were concomitant with the second, third, and probably the fourth eruption phases of the Deccan Trap LIP. Moreover, the highest Te/Th ratios is located significantly above the K/Pg boundary (+15 cm in the P0 zone), and not in the K/Pg boundary clay. Therefore, it appears that the Chicxulub bolide impact had no significant control on Te concentration herein otherwise Te enrichment in the Haymana basin should be restricted in the K/Pg boundary layer. As discussed above, similar to the Te concentration of Spitsbergen sediment that was concurrent with the Siberian Trap of the P/T boundary, the Te profile of the Haymana basin of the K/Pg transition did not show any obvious moderation by lithological and mineralogical factors like pyrite, Fe-Mn, phosphate whereas the dilution effect of carbonate-rich marl on Te and other trace elements in the Danian section was removed by Th normalisation method.

As volcanic outgassing is the major source of Te in the environment, henceforth the Te/Th variations along the Haymana sedimentary profile were possibly moderated by any concurrent massive volcanogenic emissions, for example, the Deccan Trap flood basalt. Although Hg is an accepted marker of past volcanism, the small (factor of 2) variation in Hg/Th throughout the section implies that Hg concentrations were not significantly influenced by volcanism at this location. It has to be noted that the Te/Th ratio of the Haymana section also varies by a factor 2 (Figure 25). It sounds like neither the ratio varies but, the Te/Th variation is more consistent with the U-Pb ages of Deccan volcanism – an increase in Te/Th shortly before the K/Pg boundary and high values in earliest Danian (P0) and also in P1b zones (Figure 25). Whereas highest Hg/Th values are in the late Maastrichtian, with scattered high values throughout the section which don't seem to correlate with the known timing of volcanic pulses. The dissimilarity between the observed Hg/Th and Te/Th profiles could be explained by the strong bonding of Hg with organic matter and its post-depositional secondary diagenesis.

Most of the enrichment peaks of the normalised elemental ratios suggest the onset of the major phase of emission at the K/Pg boundary (~66.03 Ma alternatively between ~66.1 to 66.0 Ma) that corresponds with 0 m of the studied profile. The other two phases occurred below (~67.5 Ma alternatively between ~66.3 to 66.15 Ma) and above (~65.12 Ma alternatively between ~65.9 to 65.8 Ma). This studied profile (starting from 66.4 Ma) occluded the 1st phase of the eruption whereas the sediment profile around +180 cm in P α zone of the Haymana basin marks the onset of the third phase of the Deccan Trap LIP eruption. The anomalous enrichments of the normalised trace element ratio (Figure 19, Figure 25) from around +180 cm to around +250 cm of the Danian were most likely caused by the

third phase of eruptions in the Deccan Trap. What's more, the significant positive correlation of Te/Th with Cd/Th ([Figure 22](#)) possibly indicates that volcanic Cd was also released during the final phase of the Deccan Trap eruption or the onset of the LDE.

The compiling of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the planktonic foraminifera ([Hull et al. 2020](#)) contemporary with the late Maastrichtian and the early Danian show intensified sea water temperature around 22.5°C and concurrent sharp fall in productivity with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ depletion reach to +0.66‰ at ~66.81 Ma. These unusual palaeoceanographic records of the Pacific were nearly parallel with anomalous enrichment of Hg/Th and Te/Th of the Haymana basin of the western Tethys Ocean around 66.03 Ma and marked the onset of the main phase of the Deccan Trap volcanic eruption at the K/Pg boundary ([Figure 26](#)). The relative discrepancy in the timeframes of the two records may reflect the geochronological disagreements of the K/Pg boundary, and the debates on $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ excursions e.g., Dan-C2 and LC29, in the Danian which have not appeared in all of the Danian sections that are recorded so far.

However, the intermittent increment in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{temp}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values of the Pacific water mass across the late Cretaceous and basal Paleogene also implies a stronger influence of the quasi-continuous Deccan Trap volcanic emissions on global temperature rise and elimination of the marine primary production during the K/Pg mass extinction. Notwithstanding, it is observed that negative carbon isotope excursions are not always intense despite the rise in temperature and *vice versa* both in the pre-K/Pg and post-K/Pg section of the ODP 1209 sediment core profile ([Hull et al. 2020](#)). The vital effects of different genera of foraminifera could be a plausible reason for this discrepant stable isotope data from the bulk carbonate analysis.

Figure 26: (A- B) Profile of Hg/Th and Te/Th of the Haymana basin, Turkey from this study during the K/Pg transition phase. (C-D) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{temp}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ of planktonic foraminifera from the Pacific Ocean (ODP 1209) (Modified from (Hull et al. 2020)) at K/Pg transition phase. (E-F) Dinoflagellate assemblage from Mudurnu–Göynük basin, NW Turkey during the K/Pg transition phase - (E) cold water dwelling *Spiniferites*, (F)- warm and oxygen stress tolerant dinoflagellate Hexaperidinioids complex (Modified from (Vellekoop et al. 2017)). The red dashed lines and the corresponding red fills indicate the K/Pg boundary layer contemporaneous with the main phase (P-2) of the Deccan Trap LIP eruption, the magenta dashed lines and corresponding magenta fills indicate the possible location of the third phase (P-3) of the Deccan Trap LIP eruption in those profiles A-F. The grey fill in the profile C-D could either represent the Dan-C2 or astronomical reasons.

The paleoredox tracers also suggest some intermittent anoxic phases in the post-K/Pg onwards across the Haymana profile with some of the most intense phases located at +15 cm (P0 zone) to +25 cm (P α zone) in the early Danian (Figure 14, Figure 19). In contrast, the parallel paleoproductivity tracers implied increased primary productions in the Haymana basin (Figure 14, Figure 19). The augmented microbial-mediated productivity for the subsequent 2 Myrs since the K/Pg event (Gibbs et al. 2020), the abundance of organic-walled phytoplankton e.g., dinoflagellate across the upper Maastrichtian to lower Danian (Brinkhuis et al. 1998; de Oca et al. 2023; Guler et al. 2019; Taylor et al. 2018; Vellekoop et al. 2015; Vellekoop et al. 2017), and the presence of diatoms in the Maastrichtian (Bergstresser & Krebs 1983; Chambers 1997) could also have their presence in the Haymana basin despite the elimination of the chlorophyllous nanoplankton to the brink during the K/Pg mass extinction and maintained high primary productivity therein (Figure 26).

If the shortest estimate of all the biozones (Keller 2014; Mateo et al. 2016) is considered then the duration of the sampled section of the Haymana basin is much less than the assumed 3-4 Myr. In fact, it is less than 1 Myr from top to bottom. If so, then both Hg/Th and Te/Th may be high in all of the studied samples and not vary much because the samples were deposited during the eruption of the Deccan Trap, and all the samples contain a volcanic input of Hg and Te.

Altogether the enriched Te/Th, Hg/Th and anomalous acmes in some of the other normalised trace elements of the Haymana basin along with the depleted $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ and high $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{temp}}$ of the Pacific water mass are suggestive of the intense environmental stress from the Deccan Trap outgassing. The Haymana sediment profile approximately from -30 cm to +30 cm was contemporaneous with that intense period of the 2nd phase of the Deccan volcanism.

Whereas the +180 cm to +220 cm of the Haymana profile was likely concomitant with the 3rd phase of the Deccan volcanism. The depleted $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ and rise in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{temp}}$ of the Pacific at 65.17 Ma most likely were parallel with the 3rd eruption phase of the Deccan Trap LIP (Figure 26). The enrichment of the trace element concentration in the youngest part of the Danian section was likely linked with the 4th phase of the Deccan volcanism and is also evident from the coexistent stable isotope variations of the contemporaneous Pacific foraminifera or resulted from the volcanoes located on the convergent plate margin of the African and Eurasian plate near the Haymana basin (Figure 26).

The depleted values of the Te/Th and Hg/Th across the Haymana profile may refer to the remobilization and deposition of Hg and Te from the earlier phases of volcanism (Regelous et al. 2020), even so, this postulation could shorten the main eruption phase (phase 2) of the Deccan Trap volcanism despite being responsible for erupting ~80% of the Deccan lava pile (Keller 2014). The updated geochronological dating (Schoene et al. 2019) agrees with a shorter phase 2 Deccan Trap eruption span. After the ~700-800 ka eruption of phase 2, the following 200-300 ka witnessed an inactive phase of the Deccan trap flood basalt (Sprain et al. 2019). During such a hiatus, the recovery of the oxidation phase in the Tethys water column and the sudden drop in primary production could be the other two important reasons for the decline in the Te/Th and Hg/Th ratio in the Early Danian P α zone (Figure 26, Figure 27). The terrigenous flux and mineralogy could also restrict the trace element variations in marine sediment.

Nevertheless, the correlation test does not find a significant effect of those environmental parameters on the Hg/Th and Te/Th variation in the Haymana basin (Figure 22) but the coexisting Hexaperidinioid dinoflagellates and shift in the microbial community could modify the Deccan Trap LIP-derived Te content in the western Tethys Ocean (Figure 27).

Since Hg is highly sensitive to organic matter, it is common to normalise Hg with TOC to remove the effect of changes in organic matter content as much as possible. On the other hand, the biological function of Te has been predicted mostly from the established Se biogeochemical cycles because of the near similarity of these two trace elements ([Symonds et al. 1987](#); [Zelenski et al. 2014](#)). Therefore, studying the Te biogeochemical cycles and exploring the Se concentration parallelly with the Te could give a better understanding of the reliability of the Te as a proxy of past volcanogenic emissions.

Figure 27: Hypothetical panorama of Haymana basin during K/Pg transition phase. (A) Lower Te/Th in Haymana basin in the absence of Deccan Trap LIP eruptions and subsequent environmental disturbances; dinoflagellate *Spiniferites* (indicated by greenish circular bodies with proboscis) and gram (+ve) microbes (represented by purple colour bodies in objective circle) were the dominant groups. (B) Higher Te/Th in Haymana basin in times of active Deccan Trap LIP eruptions and subsequent environmental disturbances; dinoflagellate Hexaperidinoids complex (indicated by greenish and yellowish cap-like bodies) and Te-reducing gram (-ve) microbes (represented by pink colour bodies in objective circle) were the dominant groups. (Modified from (Baumann et al. 2023)).

VI. CONCLUSION

The trace element variations of the Haymana basin record the environmental conditions during the latest Cretaceous to the basal Paleogene transition that was contemporaneous with the Deccan Trap flood basalt eruption in India, the Chicxulub impact in Mexico, and the K/Pg extinction event. The variations of trace elements like Mo, Ni, and As in the K/Pg boundary clay indicate the influence of bolide impact at the K/Pg boundary. However, the majority of the trace elements have intermittent enrichment and depletion excursions across the sediment profile which are shown to result from changes in lithology, redox conditions and paleoproductivity. The coexisting distal LIP in the Deccan Trap with three to four prominent eruption pulses and intermittent hiatuses could therefore be the most probable reason that caused the environmental disturbances and extinctions of the base members of the marine food web of the west Tethys in the Haymana basin.

Hg and Te, which are enriched in volcanic gas, were investigated as potential proxies for Deccan volcanism. Variations in the carbonate content have a strong control on trace element concentrations of Haymana sediments. Element concentrations were therefore normalised to Th to remove the effect of carbonate dilution. Some similarity between the Hg/Th and Te/Th variations further verifies that volcanogenic gaseous emissions might bring some of the chalcophile trace elements from the volcanic hotspot at the Deccan Trap to the distal Tethys Ocean water mass and result in their enrichments in the marine sediment bed of the Haymana basin around the K/Pg crisis.

The disparities among the paleoredox tracers like U, Mo, V, As, and Cr could be linked with continental weathering, mineralogy, and bathymetry of the Haymana basin. As well the

discrepancy in the variation of the paleoproductivity tracers like Ni, Zn, Cd, and Cu could be linked to the order of biological utilisation and the taxonomical affinity of the dominant primary producers during that time frame. The K/Pg mass extinction event led to anoxia however coexistent productivity possibly did not drop according to expectations because of the abundance of anoxic microbial groups, disaster-tolerant heterotrophic to mixotrophic groups of organic-walled dinoflagellates and probably some diatom genera. Subsequently, the profound organic matter induced organometallic bond with Hg that led to its secondary diagenesis. For this reason, in this study, the Hg/Th and Te/Th enrichment was not always parallel despite their good presence in volcanogenic aerosols.

On the other hand, phase-wise enrichment of the Te/Th appears to be consistent with radiometric ages for Deccan lavas, showing that the main phase of the Deccan volcanism began in the latest Maastrichtian and ended at the P0 zone into the Danian whereas the subsequent eruption pulses continued at least until the Danian P1b zone. In addition, the correlation analyses have suggested that the Te/Th of the Haymana basin was controlled by volcanogenic emissions from coexisting Deccan Trap LIP and not by environmental processes. Moreover, the higher Te/Th values of all Haymana samples than the average continental crust also suggest that the volcanic inputs are responsible for more than 50% of Te content Haymana basin sediment. Therefore, it could be inferred that Te/Th ratios of sediments can be used as a tracer of the paleo volcanic eruptions from the Deccan flood basalts.

Nonetheless, microalgal (dinoflagellate) primary production and anoxia-mediated microbial metabolism could modify the Te enrichment in the Haymana sediment after it had been introduced from the Deccan Trap volcanic aerosol to the Tethys Ocean. On that account, Te could also serve as a proxy for the oceanic paleoproductivity in times of severe environmental

stress although further biogeochemical observations are required to confirm this proposition. Since the main phase of Deccan volcanism seemingly overlaps in age with the Chicxulub impact and the K/Pg extinction, hence it is possible that environmental stress caused by volcanism amplified the effects of the Chicxulub impact on the biosphere and thus contributed to the K/Pg extinction event.

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LIST OF SOFTWARE USED FOR STATISTICS & GRAPHICS

1. ArcGIS Online URL <https://www.arcgis.com/index.html>
2. R Core Team (2023). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <http://www.R-project.org/>.
3. RStudio Team (2023). RStudio: Integrated Development for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA URL <http://www.rstudio.com/>.
4. PAST (4.11) URL <https://www.nhm.uio.no/english/research/resources/past/>
5. WebPlotDigitizer 4.7 URL <https://automeris.io/>
6. Inkscape-1.3.2. URL <https://inkscape.org>
7. MS Office 2016

Appendix-1

Table 1: Analysed trace element concentration from Haymana basin

Biozone	Sample ID	Depth(m)	As	Cd	Cr	Cu	La	Li	Lu	Mo	Nb	Nd	Ni	Sb	Sm	Sr	Ta	Ti	Th	V	Yb	Zn	Zr	Ba	U	Pb	Hg	Te	Re
P1b Zone	HA-130	460	16.39	0.6089	71.91	25.48	10.02	12.19	0.1191	0.6655	4.046	8.645	56.25	2.143	1.746	888	0.2669	0.1807	2.417	80.77	0.812	64.57	21.57	158.3	2.53	24.59	10.4	49.55	4.101
	HA-129	440	12.54	0.4389	142.9	32.14	15.75	33.63	0.1693	0.3056	8.702	15.34	117.1	1.296	3.131	867.9	0.5499	0.4263	5.552	110.6	1.199	89.18	52.38	312.3	3.539	17.49	27.7	103	3.803
	HA-128	420	7.16	0.4289	139.4	28.38	15.03	30.8	0.164	0.2176	7.972	14.31	104.7	0.9417	2.913	948.8	0.5058	0.3821	4.799	96.02	1.146	79.41	43.6	268.4	3.157	13.85	19.9	89.74	3.156
	HA-127	400	6.149	0.3979	114.2	26.2	13.16	25.88	0.1408	0.1946	6.616	11.93	95.19	0.8474	2.421	888.5	0.4197	0.3293	4.404	86.43	0.9787	69.42	38.37	219.1	2.965	12.05	21.8	77.92	3.818
	HA-126	380	8.311	1.109	141.5	34.13	15.3	36.26	0.1744	0.3132	8.585	13.65	114.9	1.174	2.751	806.4	0.5398	0.4867	5.562	115.2	1.22	84.44	52.21	433.2	3.483	17.47	26.6	108.9	3.119
	HA-125	360	8.866	0.5135	149.8	34.54	18.23	38.03	0.1857	0.3208	9.002	16.96	129.7	1.322	3.442	842.2	0.566	0.4836	6.073	120.5	1.29	91.65	59.11	406.9	4.32	18.83	29.5	103	3.318
	HA-124	340	8.544	0.3532	152.7	35.77	15.66	36.83	0.165	0.3071	8.928	14.72	128.4	1.168	2.958	868.8	0.5742	0.451	5.82	122.1	1.159	88.01	51.4	311.9	3.678	16.8	27.8	97.92	3.282
	HA-123	320	5.734	0.3589	94.54	21.65	11.43	23.31	0.1314	0.1893	5.684	10.31	75.87	0.7783	2.091	975.5	0.3733	0.2729	3.67	73	0.8904	57.67	31.76	175	2.952	10.07	16.1	63.75	3.226
	HA-122	300	10.26	0.3907	138	33.52	13.11	32.14	0.1508	0.2635	7.991	12.22	110.5	1.203	2.526	953.4	0.5051	0.4301	5.128	103.6	1.031	82.67	47.08	243.4	3.419	14.05	21.6	84.22	5.994
	HA-121	280	12.79	0.4719	122.7	31.71	14.9	29.12	0.161	0.318	7.682	13.49	95.97	1.195	2.743	860.5	0.4903	0.4346	5.085	100.2	1.111	78.73	47.01	279.3	3.651	16.45	26.1	79.47	5.19
	HA-120	260	9.524	0.8246	126.6	33.73	17.48	34.45	0.181	0.2981	8.347	17.48	98.56	0.9913	3.617	861.2	0.5268	0.5299	5.659	108.7	1.271	86.94	51.64	306	4.618	15.27	24.7	91.79	5.109
	HA-119	240	9.46	0.5321	166	37.68	18.56	44.67	0.1977	0.4539	9.9	17.55	134.6	1.398	3.591	726.2	0.6303	0.6127	6.546	134	1.399	108	62.47	316	4.054	20.78	33.2	115.8	3.656
HA-118	230	12.56	0.5119	172.4	47.78	15.88	49.6	0.1857	0.4831	10.75	15.52	149.8	1.957	3.169	657	0.6869	0.5957	7.279	143.7	1.301	122.4	63.17	351.4	3.512	29.21	33.9	124.9	2.41	
HA-117	220	5.911	0.6123	137.9	32.35	16.11	40.89	0.1869	0.2822	9.253	15.37	103.6	1.083	3.166	782.2	0.5824	0.5121	6.638	116.3	1.309	97.6	62.5	297.8	3.774	15.59	25.4	100	2.32	
HA-116	210	10.36	0.5599	135.3	35.02	16.47	37.94	0.166	0.3401	8.87	15.31	106.5	1.212	3.137	769.6	0.5625	0.5769	6.317	120.4	1.248	94.76	59.59	308.2	3.843	18.55	25.9	103.2	16.82	
HA-115	200	9.054	0.4752	114.1	25.86	13.73	27.79	0.1496	0.2838	6.558	12.63	87.47	1.02	2.394	881.2	0.4274	0.3716	4.406	87.93	1.028	72.36	39.7	230	3.062	12.4	19	67.06	4.141	
HA-114	190	9.701	0.4836	124.3	24.7	13.61	25.79	0.146	0.3105	6.649	12.61	82.26	0.7365	2.563	847.6	0.4246	0.331	4.354	83.67	1.027	62.02	40.18	472.4	3.015	12.17	19.3	55.71	5.182	
HA-113	180	10.55	0.4808	133.9	28.04	14.06	28.71	0.1554	0.4288	7.473	13.16	91.21	0.8776	2.699	841.1	0.4754	0.3737	5.153	95.53	1.084	76.34	45.01	450.4	3.335	13.91	22.7	63.37	4.284	
HA-112	170	14.83	0.461	139.3	28.42	15.82	30.76	0.1713	0.5287	7.941	15.03	103.5	1.727	3.076	865.1	0.4997	0.6661	5.277	105.1	1.203	96.35	51.71	400	3.506	18.54	24.6	63.21	5.757	
HA-111	160	12.74	0.6031	135.3	32.57	15.43	31.89	0.1731	0.4637	7.822	14.75	101	1.203	3.054	866.9	0.4962	0.5146	5.318	109.1	1.224	83.87	50.88	309	3.758	16.33	21.4	73.49	4.192	
HA-110	150	15.05	0.5188	117.1	23.7	12.91	25.71	0.1561	0.417	6.374	11.4	75.52	0.9865	2.331	809.6	0.4285	0.3776	4.524	80.82	1.089	63.78	43.53	237	3.402	12.56	20.9	58.76	4.55	
HA-109	140	15.56	0.4799	116.9	29.9	13.09	26.85	0.1559	0.4567	6.743	11.51	94.33	1.217	2.388	772.4	0.4382	0.4232	4.607	91.64	1.071	82.44	47.17	244.6	3.379	14.06	20.5	59.23	6.22	
HA-108	130	11.45	0.7557	131	30.88	16.99	32.78	0.1916	0.6081	8.206	15.16	100.7	0.9615	3.144	814	0.5311	0.4931	5.701	96.94	1.342	72.88	53.8	268.3	3.816	14.31	20.4	59.93	1.977	
HA-107	120	17.2	0.5994	158	43.15	18.41	41.43	0.2038	0.5305	10.07	16.87	127.3	1.263	3.45	656.5	0.6549	0.5959	6.897	125.7	1.426	88.87	67.5	354.1	4.314	19.2	29.6	87.99	4.288	
HA-106	110	19.78	0.4903	149.7	41.1	18.51	41.71	0.2001	0.3746	9.89	16.73	129.9	1.904	3.429	649.4	0.6616	0.5817	6.984	117.9	1.471	99.85	67.46	354.6	4.345	18.35	26.6	78.04	2.628	
Pa Zone	HA-105	100	18.21	0.5255	139.5	40.65	18.85	39.69	0.2122	0.3612	9.1	16.56	122.2	3.367	3.406	691.7	0.6181	0.5117	6.632	113.8	1.483	96.44	63.48	340.4	4.435	18.15	24.4	89.03	3.341
	HA-104	90	38.64	0.4842	150.6	46.38	18.3	42.71	0.2119	0.6025	9.966	16.33	145.4	1.057	3.35	644.4	0.6625	0.5854	7.12	133.7	1.477	119.4	72.54	334.9	4.327	23.27	10.2	44.26	
	HA-103	80	28.52	0.6816	159.6	47.09	18.26	44.19	0.2206	0.5952	10.23	16.7	144.7	2	3.44	619.3	0.6902	0.5427	7.481	129.6	1.414	105.9	73.65	589.1	4.85	21.04	36.3	87.74	2.75
	HA-102	70	31.11	0.58	165.1	38.6	20.28	42.76	0.231	0.5054	10.13	18.53	137.4	1.881	3.843	677.7	0.691	0.4996	7.572	120.3	1.51	105.5	70.39	396.4	5.158	19.55	29	90.72	3.639
	HA-101	60	20.92	0.5182	160.1	38	18.99	41.1	0.2218	0.4779	10.07	17.29	137.4	1.963	3.609	672.5	0.6828	0.538	7.439	117	1.564	102.2	73.98	350.5	4.549	18.48	26.6	87.66	2.556
	HA-100	50	35.58	0.5186	157.5	36.71	18.14	37.58	0.2114	0.5893	9.24	16.39	141.6	2.874	3.411	773.2	0.6219	0.4684	6.546	114.4	1.489	102	66.19	280.4	4.557	19.66	29.8	103.4	3.554
	HA-99	40	32.1	0.5302	160.7	39.97	18.64	37.96	0.2132	0.6129	9.856	17.19	151.3	2.749	3.583	679.3	0.6653	0.4784	6.935	123	1.489	101.3	67.74	313.3	4.735	20.45	35.4	113.4	2.503
	HA-98	30	8.515	0.454	72.2	20.26	9.834	16.61	0.1134	0.2289	4.205	8.423	73.94	0.8147	1.727	654.1	0.2868	0.22	2.894	60.51	0.7963	39.74	29.24	140.9	3.76	8.892	12.5	60.1	2.324
	HA-97	25	11.33	0.4723	76.94	21.96	9.145	16.74	0.1107	0.2922	4.235	8.034	81.09	0.993	1.683	654.7	0.2864	0.2703	2.918	64.31	0.7712	41.67	27.73	133.6	3.298	10.28	12.2	58.72	2.431
	HA-96	20	7.878	0.4323	86.86	22.55	10.99	19.88	0.1287	0.2426	5.185	9.767	80.91	0.7937	2.02	678.2	0.3546	0.2415	3.568	74.14	0.9044	44.6	35.37	174.9	3.492	10.38	16.4	76.14	1.799
	HA-95	15	6.822	0.3186	75.09	22.05	10.78	16.44	0.1223	0.4317	4.561	8.97	79.12	1.177	1.853	668.1	0.297	0.2217	2.978	67.11	0.8494	39.39	30.9	177	2.889	9.004	11	71.4	2.667
	HA-94	9	9.501	0.3669	113.4	25.58	13.09	24.37	0.1508	0.4201	7.104	11.44	104.7	1.717	2.351	658.5	0.4734	0.2912	4.48	94.7	1.068	57.02	45.12	269.1	3.463	13.23	14.8	97.1	1.262
HA-93	7	7.625	0.3943	121.6	28.23	14.89	26.43	0.1651	0.3122	7.438	13.15	113.6	1.066	2.708	656.8	0.4935	0.2991	4.727	103.6	1.14	61.13	48.9	332	3.459	12.96	24.4	105.4	2.305	
HA-92	3	6.038	0.3815	146.6	30.86	17.4	28.94	0.1779	0.3261	8.538	15.05	139	0.884	3.056	626.4	0.5715	0.3207	5.262	110.8	1.255	64.88	54.2	389.6	3.206	11.8	14.1	108.9	2.494	
HA-91	1	13.09	0.4237	185.3	38.17	18.44	38.59	0.1964	0.715	10.7	16.27	180.8	1.745	3.334	560.5	0.6846	0.4516	6.238	140	1.354	78.78	69.98	920	3.849	15.51	36.8	134.7	4.017	
K/Pg	HA-90	0	79.93	0.6917	252	67.7	15.73	42.92	0.247	37.92	12.03	17.5	534.7	10.79	3.977	702.1	0.8162	0.9629	7.795	180	1.762	123.9	85.02	8759	7.696	58.76	170.5	3.026	

Appendix-2

Table 2: Linear regression and correlation values of selective trace elements from r-programme

Elements (y & x)	P- value	Relation	Estimated Std. (m)	Intercept (c)	R ²	Pearson's product-moment correlation (R) [95% CI]
Hg & Th	<2e-16	Significant	4.6269	-0.976	0.5847	0.7646806
Te & Th	2.27E-13	Significant	9.617	31.074	0.3484	0.5902284
Re & Th	0.23515	Insignificant	-0.4304	6.5296	0.01117	-0.105678
Nb & Th	<2e-16	Significant	1.55683	-0.02864	0.9191	0.9586743
Ni & Th	<2e-16	Significant	30.78	-39.37	0.4653	0.6821209
Tl & Th	1.38E-14	Significant	0.135995	0.048293	0.3763	0.6134349
Sr & Th	<2e-16	Significant	-76.52	1103.25	0.4293	-0.6552116
Sm & Yb	<2e-16	Significant	2.5879	-0.2547	0.7766	0.881239
Mo & Re	0.0803	Insignificant	-0.00561	0.379953	0.02427	-0.15577

Appendix-3

Figure I: Eruption chronology of the Deccan Trap LIP in Western Ghat, India. (A) represents composite stratigraphic thickness, and (B) represents cumulative volume versus age of the formations. (Modified from Renne et al, 2015).

